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EDITORIAL

EDITORIAL

Message from the Editor-in-Chief of
International Journal of Science Annals, 2024

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Background and Aim of Study:	Abstract <i>The publication of scientific papers in the media is becoming more and more accessible. This creates competition between scientific journals. It can ensure an increase in the scientific level of published products. The aim of the study: to familiarise both the readers and the authors with the activities of the International Journal of Science Annals (IJSA).</i>
Results:	<i>The results of the journal's activities over the past year and its future prospects were analysed. Authors were informed about the benefits of publishing in the IJSA and about the possibility of participating in international scientific events (conferences, competitions) organised with the participation of the journal.</i>
Conclusions:	<i>The high competition in the publishing market requires the IJSA to systematically improve the scientific level of the journal, to adhere to high publishing standards and ethical norms, to create coordinated, productive relationships between authors and reviewers, and to provide them with new opportunities.</i>
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Introduction

Scientific publications are the most effective way to share your research with the relevant experts and the general public.

The popularity of a particular journal among readers is determined by interest in its content and accessibility. While the popularity of a journal among authors is often due to its brand and its inclusion in certain scientometric databases.

International scientometric databases, repositories and search engines, as well as free and open access to scientific research, have created favourable conditions for authors to disseminate their ideas to colleagues and society. This has removed a number of constraints (availability, scope of distribution, number of copies, cost, etc.).

Results

Analysis of the Journal Activity

A book, journal or other type of printed (paper) publication, as a material phenomenon of human culture, is increasingly likely to cease to exist in the future as it is converted to an electronic format.

Long-established journals have already registered and are publishing online versions of their issues today. However, they still continue to publish print versions. Maybe it is because of the registration obligations. But one would hope that the cultural traditions and ethical principles of publishers are the reason for this. The IJSA has print and online ISSNs. Printed copies are sent to leading libraries and universities. It has a positive impact on the author's citation index and the university's position in international rankings.

The IJSA has a highly qualified team of reviewers. The website provides a set of mandatory criteria for manuscript evaluation. Response form templates developed for authors. Authors can appeal against reviews and the editor's decision. The IJSA Editorial Board includes the most authoritative scientists in the fields of Education, Psychology and Medicine from 17 countries and 5 continents. We guarantee compliance with the appropriate level of publication ethics and copyright protection at all stages of material review. The IJSA is a member of the Committee of Publication Ethics (COPE, 2024).

The IJSA Editorial Office is very strict about plagiarism. The Journal offers three levels of plagiarism checking for a manuscript. The first level is carried out by the author when submitting the manuscript. The second level is carried out by the editorial staff. The third level can be carried out by the reader if similarities are detected. For this purpose, the website has a "Submit an appeal against plagiarism" function.

The IJSA has a sophisticated, multi-functional website that provides authors with access to paper templates and supporting documents. The website also has personal pages for each of the authors.

In 2023, the Editorial Office received 119 manuscripts, of which: 14 were published, 105 were rejected. The average number of rejected manuscripts is 85%, of which: 40% are rejected during the preliminary evaluation process; 45% are rejected during the peer review process. We have considered the issue of quality and quantity of scientific publications (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2021).

The IJSA is represented at universities and in more than 160 libraries around the world. Present in over 40 international scientometric databases, repositories and search engines.

Future Journal Activity Directions

KRPOCH Publishing and the Editorial Board take into account current trends in scientific publishing (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2023; Pypenko, 2023), based on which the journal development plan for the next 5 years has been developed.

KRPOCH Publishing, in collaboration with the IJSA, organises annual international scientific conferences on Current Issues of Education and Science, and Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Modern Specialist Formation. At conferences, all authors are invited to present a report. IJSA authors pay no registration fee to attend these scientific events and have the opportunity to present their research to all conference participants. In addition, the authors' presentations are

available in open access on the official YouTube channel of the KRPOCH conferences.

KRPOCH Publishing organises annual scientific competitions, including International Competition Mental Health in the Digital Society (ICMHDS-2024). KRPOCH Publishing covers the full cost of publishing manuscripts submitted to the competition in the IJSA. It motivates young researchers.

Papers focusing on digitalisation and the use of artificial intelligence in education and medicine are a priority for the current issue of IJSA.

In January 2024, the IJSA has been submitted for a pre-evaluation report for inclusion in Scopus and for evaluation by the Web of Science editorial team (status – under evaluation).

Conclusions

The IJSA adheres to high publishing standards and ethical norms. The journal combines the requirements of the reviewers and the views of the authors. The journal organises international events where it creates and provides a platform to promote the ideas of IJSA authors. Despite all the difficulties that the KRPOCH Publishing house and the IJSA Office have experienced in connection with the military aggression against Ukraine, we continue to move forward.

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**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES**

Education

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Education

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Artificial Intelligence as a Factor Revolutionizing Higher Education

Authors' Contribution:
A – Study design;
B – Data collection;
C – Statistical analysis;
D – Data interpretation;
E – Manuscript preparation;
F – Literature search;
G – Funds collection

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Abstract

The use of artificial intelligence and various chatbots based on it is becoming part of everyday higher education practice. The aim of the study: to explore practices and identify trends in the use of artificial intelligence-based chatbots by higher education stakeholders.

The survey was conducted between January and April 2024. The total number of respondents from 57 countries was 788, of whom 363 were students and 425 were university faculty. The probability sampling method was applied. Respondents were interviewed online. The questionnaire is available on the official website of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH using Google Forms, as well as on social networks Facebook, LinkedIn, etc. for potential participants. In addition, a selective individual online interview was conducted with respondents. Cronbach's alpha confirmed adequate internal consistency ($\alpha=0.837$).

The role of artificial intelligence-based chatbots in higher education practice was considered. The use of chatbots among higher education stakeholders (students and faculty) was studied. A model of stakeholder behaviour was developed. This model describes two ways of solving problems: with and without the use of artificial intelligence. Trends in the use of chatbots in higher education were identified: students were 26.9% more likely than faculty to use artificial intelligence-based chatbots to prepare for classes or complete assignments at their college/university; almost all students (68.0% of 68.3% who use chatbots) edited the results returned by generative chatbots at their request; students were 30.1% more likely than faculty to edit these results.

The new technologies of generative artificial intelligence have been the factors that have revolutionised the industry of higher education. A new “Human-AI” system has emerged that is fundamentally changing the rules for training young professionals. The study emphasizes that higher education stakeholders using chatbots should do so correctly, consider the possibilities and limitations of using this toolkit, and recognize their responsibility for the outcomes and consequences of their use.

education, artificial intelligence, chatbots, Human-AI system, interaction, responsibility, stakeholder

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Introduction

Society has entered an era of digitalisation. This has opened up new perspectives for the study and use of artificial intelligence (Pypenko, 2019). The higher education industry is one of the first sectors of human endeavour to embark on digital transformation (Shenkoya & Kim, 2023). The number of studies and publications on the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in higher education has increased two to three times in the last five years compared to previous years (Bearman et al., 2023; Chu et al., 2022; Crompton & Burke, 2023). The advent of chatbots based on artificial intelligence (AI chatbots) and specialised in text (Large Language Models) has been a catalyst and a major factor in revolutionising higher education. These changes are in progress at this moment. The changes affect all elements of the higher education system and all stakeholders involved in the process. Today, we are seeing a boom in the use of various AI-based chatbots by faculty and students in the educational process.

As a result, many new questions arise about the legitimacy of using AI and adhering to ethical standards when using AI chatbots in education and science (Melnik & Pypenko, 2023). Therefore, there is an obvious need to study the influence and role of AI in the research and teaching activities of professors and the learning activities of university students.

The aim of the study. To explore practices and identify trends in the use of artificial intelligence-based chatbots by stakeholders in higher education.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted among 363 students (175 males and 188 females) and 425 university faculty (198 males and 227 females) from 57 countries between January and April 2024. The probability sampling method (randomly generated) was used to survey faculty working in hybrid modes in higher education. A similar method was used to survey students who were studying synchronous contact and distance learning or asynchronous distance learning. The survey was voluntary. Participation was anonymous. Respondents were interviewed online.

The questionnaire was available on the official website of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH using Google Forms

(https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeu0HZW1t715guMH7M_FcTDizHxnpU-OvPMU1_ICfPF_K9y6g/viewform). The questionnaire was also made available to potential participants on social networking sites such as Facebook, LinkedIn, etc. A selective individualised online interview was also conducted with survey participants, when it was necessary to clarify their answers and/or determine the specifics of their use of AI chatbots.

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 28.0.1 software. Descriptive statistics using frequencies, means and standard deviations were used to analyze the data collected. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha was 0.837. This meets internal consistency requirements ($\alpha > 0.7$).

Results

The questionnaire developed consisted of six questions. It was used to gather information about the possibilities of using AI chatbots in higher education. The questionnaire consisted of an instruction sheet explaining the purpose and conditions of the study and six questions, of which three questions characterised the respondent (gender, status, country) and three questions related to the purpose of the study.

To explore how stakeholders are using AI chatbots in higher education, the following general questions apply:

A. Does your college/university use hybrid learning (face-to-face / distance learning)?

B. Do you use artificial intelligence-based chatbots to prepare for classes or complete assignments at your college/university?

C. Do you edit the results returned by generative chatbots at your request?

The questions involved the choice of one of the answer options "yes" or "no".

The key findings of the study on the use of artificial intelligence-based chatbots by higher education stakeholders are summarized in Tables 1–3.

Table 1

Comparative Characteristics of the Use of Hybrid (Face-to-Face/Distance) Learning by Higher Education Stakeholders

Higher education stakeholders	Answer to question A				Total	
	Positive		Negative		people	%
	people	%	people	%		
Students	315	86.8	48	13.2	363	100.0
Male	141	38.8	34	9.4	175	48.2
Female	174	47.9	14	3.9	188	51.8
Faculty	353	83.1	72	16.9	425	100.0
Male	178	41.9	20	4.7	198	46.6
Female	175	41.2	52	12.2	227	53.4
Total	668	84.8	120	15.2	788	100.0
Male	319	40.5	54	6.9	373	47.3
Female	349	44.3	66	8.4	415	52.7

Table 2

Comparative Characteristics of Higher Education Stakeholders' Use of Artificial Intelligence-Based Chatbots to Prepare for Classes or Complete Assignments at Their College/University

Higher education stakeholders	Answer to question B				Total	
	Positive		Negative		people	%
	people	%	people	%		
Students	248	68.3	115	31.7	363	100.0
Male	121	33.3	54	14.9	175	48.2
Female	127	35.0	61	16.8	188	51.8
Faculty	176	41.4	249	58.6	425	100.0
Male	81	19.1	117	27.5	198	46.6
Female	95	22.4	132	31.1	227	53.4
Total	424	53.8	364	46.2	788	100.0
Male	202	25.6	171	21.7	373	47.3
Female	222	28.2	193	24.5	415	52.7

Table 3

Comparative Characteristics of the Processing of the Results Returned by the Generative Chatbot at the Request of Higher Education Stakeholders

Higher education stakeholders	Answer to question C				Total	
	Positive		Negative		people	%
	people	%	people	%		
Students	247	68.0	116	32.0	363	100.0
Male	124	34.2	51	14.0	175	48.2
Female	123	33.9	65	17.9	188	51.8
Faculty	161	37.9	264	62.1	425	100.0
Male	88	20.7	110	25.9	198	46.6
Female	73	17.2	154	36.2	227	53.4
Total	408	51.8	380	48.2	788	100.0
Male	212	26.9	161	20.4	373	47.3
Female	196	24.9	219	27.8	415	52.7

The results showed that 84.8% (668 people) of the stakeholders have the possibility of hybrid (face-to-face/distance) learning in their college/university, including 40.5% (319 people) males and 44.3% (349 people) females. Only 15.2% (120 people), of whom 6.9% (54 people) were male and 8.4% (66 people) were female, do not use hybrid learning.

53.8% (424 people), including 25.6% (202 people) males and 28.2% (222 people) females, use artificial intelligence-based chatbots to prepare for classes or complete assignments at their college/university.

A negative answer to question B was given by 46.2% (364 people) of the stakeholders, of whom 21.7% (171 people) were male and 24.5% (193 people) were female. Overall, the results returned by generative chatbots are edited by 51.8% (408 people) of stakeholders, including 26.9% (212 people) men and 24.9% (196 people) women. Slightly less than half of the stakeholders (48.2% or 380 people) do not edit the results, of whom 20.4% (161 people) were male and 27.8% (219 people) were female.

The comparative characteristics of the use of artificial intelligence-based chatbots by stakeholders of higher education (students and university faculty) at their college/university are shown in Figures 1–3.

The comparative characteristics of stakeholders showed that 86.8% (315 people) of students, including 38.8% (141 people) males and 47.9% (174 people) females, and 83.1% (353 people) of faculty, including 41.9% (178 people) males and 41.2% (175 people) females, use hybrid (face-to-face/distance) learning in their college/university. Only 13.2% (48 people) of students, of whom 9.4% (34 people) were male and 3.9% (14 people) were female, and 16.9% (72 people) of faculty, of whom 4.7% (20 people) were male and 12.2% (52 people) were female, do not use hybrid learning.

The comparative characteristics of higher education stakeholders who use of artificial intelligence-based chatbots to prepare for classes or complete assignments at their college/university showed that 68.3% (248 people) of students, of whom 33.3% (121 people) were male and 35.0% (127 people) were female, use of AI-based chatbots. Consequently, 31.7% (115 people) of the students do not, including 14.9% (54 people) males and 16.8% (61 people) females.

A different trend is observed among faculty. Only 41.4% (176 faculty), including 19.1% (81 people) males and 22.4% (95 people) females, use artificial intelligence-based chatbots to prepare for classes or complete assignments at their college/university.

Figure 1

Use of Hybrid (Face-to-Face/Distance) Learning by Higher Education Stakeholders (Students and Faculty) at Their College/University

Figure 2

Use of Artificial Intelligence-Based Chatbots by Higher Education Stakeholders (Students and Faculty) to Prepare for Classes or Complete Assignments at Their College/University

Figure 3

Processing of Results by Higher Education Stakeholders (Students and Faculty) Returned by Generative Chatbots

In other words, more than half of the faculty (58.6% or 249 people, of whom 27.5% or 117 people were male and 31.1% or 132 people were female) do not use it. The comparative characteristics of higher education stakeholders who process of the results returned by generative chatbots at their request showed that 68.0%

(247 people) of students, of whom 34.2% (124 people) were male and 33.9% (123 people) were female, edit the results. Accordingly, 32.0% (116 people) of the students do not edit, including 14.0% (51 people) males and 17.9% (65 people) females.

The trend is different for faculty. Only 37.9% (161 faculty), including 20.7% (88 people) males and 17.2% (73 people) females, edit of the results returned by generative chatbots at their request. That is, more than 60.0% of the faculty (62.1% or 264 people, of whom

25.9% or 110 people were male and 36.2% or 154 people were female) do not edit.

The comparative characteristics of the respondents (higher education stakeholders), grouped by country, are presented in Table 4.

Table 4
Comparative Characteristics of Respondents Grouped by Country

Country	Respondents, people		Respondents, %		Respondents, people		Respondents, %		Respondents, total	
	Students	Faculty	Students	Faculty	Male	Female	Male	Female	People	%
US	21	24	2.7	3.0	31	14	3.9	1.8	45	5.7
India	23	21	2.9	2.7	21	23	2.7	2.9	44	5.6
Ukraine	36	3	4.6	0.4	4	35	0.6	4.4	39	4.9
Indonesia	21	18	2.7	2.3	25	14	3.2	1.8	39	4.9
Singapore	16	19	2.0	2.4	16	19	2.0	2.4	35	4.4
China	18	16	2.3	2.0	15	19	1.9	2.4	34	4.3
UK	18	15	2.3	1.9	16	17	2.0	2.2	33	4.2
Canada	17	14	2.2	1.8	12	19	1.5	2.4	31	3.9
Japan	16	14	2.0	1.8	14	16	1.8	2.0	30	3.8
Australia	15	13	1.9	1.6	11	17	1.4	2.2	28	3.6
Portugal	11	16	1.4	2.0	10	17	1.3	2.2	27	3.4
Germany	8	18	1.0	2.3	12	14	1.6	1.7	26	3.3
France	11	15	1.4	1.9	12	14	1.6	1.7	26	3.3
Spain	10	14	1.3	1.8	11	13	1.5	1.6	24	3.0
Italy	10	11	1.3	1.4	9	12	1.1	1.5	21	2.7
Brazil	9	12	1.1	1.5	10	11	1.3	1.4	21	2.7
Philippines	12	8	1.5	1.0	8	12	1.0	1.5	20	2.5
Austria	10	8	1.3	1.0	10	8	1.3	1.0	18	2.3
Denmark	8	5	1.0	0.6	4	9	0.5	1.1	13	1.6
Ireland	2	10	0.3	1.3	6	6	0.7	0.8	12	1.5
Israel	9	3	1.1	0.4	5	7	0.6	0.9	12	1.5
Sweden	5	6	0.6	0.8	6	5	0.7	0.7	11	1.4
South Africa	2	8	0.3	1.0	5	5	0.7	0.6	10	1.3
South Korea	3	7	0.4	0.9	4	6	0.5	0.8	10	1.3
New Zealand	6	5	0.8	0.6	6	5	0.7	0.7	11	1.4
UAE	2	7	0.3	0.9	5	4	0.6	0.5	9	1.1
Finland	1	8	0.1	1.0	5	4	0.6	0.5	9	1.1
Czech Republic	3	5	0.4	0.6	3	5	0.4	0.6	8	1.0
Argentina	1	6	0.1	0.8	4	3	0.5	0.4	7	0.9
Poland	3	4	0.4	0.5	4	3	0.5	0.4	7	0.9
Estonia	1	6	0.1	0.8	3	4	0.4	0.5	7	0.9
Switzerland	2	5	0.3	0.6	4	3	0.5	0.4	7	0.9
Lithuania	1	5	0.1	0.6	2	4	0.3	0.5	6	0.8
Belgium	0	6	0.0	0.8	3	3	0.4	0.4	6	0.8
Mexico	0	6	0.0	0.8	2	4	0.3	0.5	6	0.8
Saudi Arabia	2	4	0.3	0.5	4	2	0.5	0.3	6	0.8
Nigeria	1	5	0.1	0.6	5	1	0.6	0.1	6	0.8
Malaysia	2	4	0.3	0.5	3	3	0.4	0.4	6	0.8
Romania	0	6	0.0	0.8	2	4	0.3	0.5	6	0.8
Greece	1	4	0.1	0.5	1	4	0.1	0.5	5	0.6
Iceland	4	1	0.5	0.1	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Tunisia	2	3	0.3	0.4	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Latvia	2	3	0.3	0.4	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Norway	1	4	0.1	0.5	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Slovakia	1	4	0.1	0.5	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Turkey	0	5	0.0	0.6	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Netherlands	3	2	0.4	0.3	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Thailand	2	3	0.3	0.4	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Taiwan	1	4	0.1	0.5	3	2	0.3	0.3	5	0.6
Oman	3	1	0.4	0.1	3	1	0.4	0.1	4	0.5
Algeria	0	4	0.0	0.5	3	1	0.4	0.1	4	0.5
Bahrain	2	1	0.3	0.1	3	0	0.4	0.0	3	0.4
Colombia	1	2	0.1	0.3	2	1	0.2	0.2	3	0.4
Benin	2	0	0.3	0.0	2	0	0.3	0.0	2	0.3
Iraq	0	2	0.0	0.3	2	0	0.3	0.0	2	0.3
Kenya	1	1	0.1	0.1	1	1	0.1	0.1	2	0.3
Peru	1	1	0.1	0.1	1	1	0.1	0.1	2	0.3
Total	363	425	46.1	53.9	373	415	47.3	52.7	788	100.0

Respondents from the following countries have the highest representation:

- US (5.7%, including 2.7% students and 3.0% faculty, of whom 3.9% were male and 1.8% were female);
- India (5.6%, including 2.9% students and 2.7% faculty, of whom 2.7% were male and 2.9% were female);
- Ukraine (4.9%, including 4.6% students and 0.4% faculty, of whom 0.6% were male and 4.4% were female);
- Indonesia (4.9%, including 2.7% students and 2.3% faculty, of whom 3.2% were male and 1.8% were female);
- Singapore (4.4%, including 2.0% students and 2.4% faculty, of whom 2.0% were male and 2.4% were female);
- China (4.3%, including 2.3% students and 2.0% faculty, of whom 1.9% were male and 2.4% were female);
- UK (4.2%, including 2.3% students and 1.9% faculty, of whom 2.0% were male and 2.2% were female).

Thus, the survey conducted among 363 university students and 425 university faculty from 57 countries allowed to obtain quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the use of AI chatbots in higher education. Importantly, students are 26.9% more likely than faculty to use AI-based chatbots to prepare for classes or complete assignments at their college/university. At the same time, almost all students (68.0% of 68.3% who use AI-based chatbots) edit the results returned by generative chatbots at their request. In addition, students are 30.1% more likely to edit these results than faculty.

Discussion

As AI develops in society and AI chatbots are used in higher education, this area is becoming increasingly important for research. Experts predict that the use of artificial intelligence in education will grow by 43.0% between 2018 and 2022 (Educause, 2018). But already in the 2019 Horizon Report for higher education (Educause, 2019), predictions about teaching and learning with AI applications have become even more optimistic. As practice has shown, they were fully justified.

In the first two months of OpenAI's ChatGPT, more than 100 million people became its active users. According to Reuters (Hu, 2023), the analysts note that in the last 20 years in the Internet space, it is hard to remember a faster growth rate for consumer Internet applications.

At first glance, the prospects look promising for students and faculty who have already begun to use AI-based tools. There is a growing consensus among researchers about the revolutionary impact of AI on learning and teaching in higher education (Alqahtani et al., 2023; O'Dea & O'Dea, 2023; Rahiman & Kodikal, 2024).

Because revolutionary impact can affect the way people live, as well as education, health, the economy and other areas of society, we limited our study to the higher education sector. However, this restriction is conditional, as these areas are closely intertwined in

higher education and the AI phenomenon is of interdisciplinary interest to the scientific community. AI chatbots are a tool used in a variety of interdisciplinary research and subject areas, including education (Doroudi, 2023; Shrivastava, 2023), psychological research in education (Bonneton et al., 2024; Melnyk, 2023), and medical education (Civaner et al., 2022; Masters, 2019), among others.

The most pressing issue in research into the revolutionary impact of AI on learning and teaching in higher education has been the following question: Is there compelling evidence that AI can have a positive pedagogical impact on students and be a reliable tool in the teaching and research process?

O'Dea and O'Dea (2023) argue that there is as yet no reliable evidence of how the use of AI technologies and applications has helped students improve their learning and/or helped faculty make effective pedagogical changes.

There is also an opposing point of view. A group of researchers claim that the introduction of AI has led to the development of robust assessment methods and increased teacher engagement (Rahiman & Kodikal, 2024); AI can shape future education and research practices, leading to better outcomes (Alqahtani et al., 2023), and radically transform and improve the way learning and teaching takes place in higher education institutions (Mishra, 2019).

Researchers on the digital transformation of the higher education sector take a similar view. These academics argue that digital transformation will lead to the development of sustainable curricula, the digitisation of higher education, increased innovation and improved student outcomes (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2021; Shenkoya & Kim, 2023).

In recent years, a growing number of researchers have argued that the implementation of AI is the most optimistic solution for improving education (Chedrawi & Howayeck, 2019). It suggests ways in which universities can change their role to respond quickly and effectively to emerging issues.

These may include new courses, but also organisational structures and new pedagogical practices (Moscardini et al., 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of online technologies in higher education (Bartolic et al., 2022; Pypenko, et al., 2020) and the associated opportunities for AI-mediated student-teacher interaction (Rof et al., 2022).

Some researchers believe that the widespread availability of online learning platforms at universities has made it possible to study courses and training programmes to obtain degrees entirely online (Dieguez et al., 2021).

It is therefore possible that the use of online learning platforms is one of the reasons for the active development and application of AI in higher education. Therefore, one of our research questions is to investigate how the use of hybrid learning (face-to-face/distance learning) in higher education has influenced the use of AI tools among stakeholders.

The results show that there is a positive correlation between hybrid learning and the use of AI chatbots among students and faculty.

The results of our study, and the willingness of students to use AI chatbots in their education, are consistent with research on trends in the potential application of AI-based robots in higher education. Research shows that students are ready to use them in their education (AlGerafi et al., 2023). This, in turn, is a signal to university administrators. They should pay attention to the social demands of today's youth.

A key benefit of using AI in higher education is its ability to drive efficiency, personalisation and optimisation of administrative processes (Al Husseiny, 2023).

Examining global trends in the use of AI and their implications for changing educational paradigms highlights the role of collaboration and partnership in fostering innovation that, by setting new quality standards, stimulates the evolution of higher education (Aithal & Maiya, 2023).

With the advent of AI, the modern world has begun to change rapidly. And it is highly likely that the new Human-AI system will radically change the rules of student education in universities (Melnik & Pypenko, 2023).

In our view, the main problem with using AI in learning and teaching in higher education is getting the result without any human effort. We have presented a model of stakeholder behaviour in Figure 4.

Figure 4

A Model of Stakeholder Behaviour Describing two Options for Problem Solving: With and Without the Use of Artificial Intelligence

The model developed shows that stakeholders can use the following options to achieve their objectives.

The first option involves personal effort on the part of the stakeholder, using all available knowledge, skills, competencies and experience to achieve a result.

The second option involves the use of AI to achieve a result without any personal effort on the part of the stakeholder.

Interviewing students in the study revealed that they are actively using the help of AI chatbots in their studies, because it is personalised and delivers results in the shortest possible time. As a result, students are increasingly using AI chatbots to complete academic tasks. These activities increase the risk of students dropping out or experiencing academic difficulties.

In our view, AI tools can be useful for analysing information, searching and framing literature, and even to some extent for generating ideas.

However, rewriting (copying) the text generated by AI chatbots is not sufficient to fulfil the curriculum and is against ethical principles. In addition, search engines and plagiarism detection systems may consider such text to be duplicate content. This can have negative consequences for higher education stakeholders.

As we can see from the results of our survey, one of the most common ways to avoid duplicating or borrowing other people's work, and to make the result more original, is to edit the text generated by the AI. This tendency is more pronounced among students (68.0%) and less pronounced among faculty (37.9%).

It is possible that the use of AI chatbots by students and faculty, followed by editing and creative reinterpretation of the results, could be an intermediate, optimal way for them to interact with AI.

It should be noted that at the current stage of social and technological development, the issue of Human-AI

interaction remains unresolved. It still requires the development, ratification and implementation of laws governing the norms of interaction and relationships between humans and AI (Pypenko, 2023).

We believe that it is premature to declare a predominantly positive role for AI in higher education, given the current stage of AI development, the extent of its prevalence in higher education, and the lack of research on the subject. What is clear, however, is the revolutionary impact of AI on higher education.

Our research (questionnaires and interviews) showed that AI implementations at the institutional level were more likely to be initiated and implemented by students and faculty than by university administrators. Possible reasons for this are the need and the lack of readiness of administrations to upgrade the existing technological infrastructure of universities, and to introduce specialised courses for students and to organise professional development courses for faculty in the field of AI.

Conclusions

New generative artificial intelligence technologies are rapidly gaining popularity and have already become an integral part of the higher education industry. The new Human-AI system is fundamentally changing the rules of student education at universities.

AI tools can be useful for information analysis, literature searches and framing, and even to some extent for idea generation. However, rewriting text generated by AI chatbots may not be enough to produce high-quality original work. It is also in conflict with the ethical principles of scientific research. In addition, such text may be considered as duplicate content by search engines and plagiarism detection systems.

It is therefore appropriate not only to edit the text generated by AI chatbots (which is often limited to

faculty and students), but also to add value to the text in the form of information or an idea that should be developed from one's own world view to create something new and original.

Higher education stakeholders should be made aware that AI chatbots are just a tool that needs to be used properly, taking into account their capabilities and limitations. It is especially important to send a message to higher education stakeholders that when they use AI chatbots in their work, they are responsible for the outcomes and consequences of their use.

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Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee. Permission for research received in the Research Committee of virtue and ethics Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (protocol No. 023-2/SRIKRPOCH dated 10.08.2023). Informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

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SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Education

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

A Digital Leap in the Evolution of Continuous Professional Development for Teachers

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The realm of education is in a constant state of evolution, necessitating that teachers at K-12 and tertiary levels continually update their practices through continuous professional development (CPD). The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly accelerated the adoption of online CPD, encompassing self-driven initiatives, government-led programs, and third-party offerings, notably those by the British Council in the MENA region, which is the emphasis of this study. This transition to online platforms initially involved leveraging Zoom, and subsequently, WhatsApp.

The aim of the study: to map the process of CPD-infused online training by analyzing meeting schedules, topics discussed, group dynamics, and interaction patterns. Additionally, it seeks to develop a CPD-based system that can be replicated or scaled for broader implementation.

Material and Methods:

This descriptive multi-case study is conducted on two WhatsApp groups dedicated to enhancing the skills and competencies of 990 and 780 MENA teachers, respectively. For data collection, the study employed two primary tools: participant observation, and analysis of archived data from CPD-based multimedia-focused discussions in both e-groups over a fixed period of 40 days.

Results:

The research provides a comprehensive overview of the CPD process and a cost-effective scalable CPD-centric system based on six key elements: e-platforms, e-meetings, archiving, certification, website and organization that orchestrates and streamlines the entire process. This CPD-driven system offers guidelines for institutions and policymakers looking to replicate this system in their educational contexts, with the goal of upgrading teachers' pedagogical expertise.

Conclusions:

This study contributes to understanding the effectiveness and scalability of online CPD initiatives using platforms like WhatsApp, particularly in regions like MENA, and offers insights for stakeholders aiming to implement similar strategies for enhancing teacher professional development.

Keywords:

education, system, social media, CPD, MENA, WhatsApp

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Introduction

In these turbulent times, professional continuous development for teachers at all levels, including primary, middle, secondary, and tertiary, is becoming increasingly crucial. It enables them to sharpen their capabilities, broaden their pedagogical repertoire, and build upon existing knowledge to overall enhance the teaching profession. In this sense, the landscape of education is being fundamentally changed by technology, as digital advancements progressively integrate into the daily tasks of teachers in schools (Player-Koro et al., 2018; Pypenko, 2019). In fact, technology has been a proficient vessel through which continuous professional development (CPD) has transcended the physical confines of educational institutions, thereby becoming more widespread.

Accordingly, a consistent body of literature has been produced in term of using CPD online for teachers (e.g., Çelen & Seferoglu, 2020; Lantz-Andersson et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2023). Along these lines, the pandemic has significantly accelerated the proliferation of technologizing CPD programs because instructors worldwide were in need to upgrade their e-savoir-faire to be able to operate in online-only environment in the wide spectrum of pedagogical facets. During these times, different initiative be it self-initiated (Rahman et al., 2020), government-mandated (Mutiary & Ratnam-Lim, 2023) and/or third party-led as it is the case in this study.

In this respect, it's attested that teacher training encompass training instructors to hone different competences (Hossein et al., 2024) that ranges from creating educational tasks that cater to the specific needs of students (Simamora et al., 2020; Thumiki & Magd, 2022), utilizing precise, organized content and schedule to impart course requirements to learners (Jung et al., 2021; Li et al., 2017), devising online pedagogical materials in/for learning management system (LMS) (González et al., 2023; Martin et al., 2019), choosing suitable online technology that aligns with the desired content and learning objectives (Adi Badiozaman et al., 2022; Schalk et al., 2022), creating a well-structured course with supplementary tips, instructions, and criteria (Paliwal & Singh, 2021; Wang et al., 2021), to efficiently aligning learning goals, course tasks, assessment methods, and educational activities in online courses (Hung & Chou, 2015; Reader et al., 2020), and creating online study materials, methodologies, and resources to enhance learning effectiveness and organization (Metz & Bezuidenhout, 2018; Phelps & Vlachopoulos, 2019).

Additionally, these teacher training (e)-programs were conducted on educational platforms including Zoom (e.g., Anene & Idiedo, 2023; Lucovich, 2021) and Google meet (Noor et al., 2021) along with other informal arenas including social media (Acuyo, 2021; Maloney et al., 2017) such as twitter (e.g. Colwell & Hutchison, 2018), Facebook (e.g., Al-Jarf, 2021; Bett & Makewa, 2020) and more importantly WhatsApp (Kihwele & Mgata, 2022). These social media-facilitated professional development programs are

especially useful for average to low-resourced contexts (Focho, 2023) where it become significantly cost-effective to deploy such e-trainings and to larger audience. As a result, it is recommended that social media tools like WhatsApp hold promise for fostering teacher development in similar under-privileged contexts (Motteram et al., 2020).

Further, another key advantage of professional development facilitated by social media is its flexibility to tailor to the specific needs of different teachers and accommodate an individual's changing requirements as they progress through various stages of their career (Anders, 2018). For this reason, Acuyo (2021) urges tutors to utilize the interactive functions of social media platforms to connect with fellow professionals and make a lasting impact in the community by actively participating in online discussions.

In a more angled standpoint, different studies that have been conducted on how to leverage WhatsApp for continuous professional developments ends. In this regard, Cansoy (2017) suggests that WhatsApp groups have the potential to facilitate professional growth by offering field expertise, pedagogical knowledge, practical teaching insights, and emotional encouragement among educators. With its wide range of functions, many social media-based features can be utilized for educational purposes in general and specifically for professional development.

Another investigation conducted by Motteram et al. (2020) suggests that WhatsApp groups enhanced teachers' proficiency in English language, offering a forum for sharing and discussing challenges specific to their context, facilitating the creation of teaching materials, and initiating meaningful discussions to address issues. It also highlights concerns regarding participation, access, equity, and sustainability highlighting the potential of online platforms in enhancing teacher professional growth and the associated advantages. In the same veins, Lee et al. (2023) found similar outcomes in a primary school situated in Hong Kong amidst the COVID-19 crisis, determining that WhatsApp can aid in fostering continual professional growth for teachers primarily that of English as a second language.

On the flip side, Mohr and Shelton (2017) reported that most of these training programs "typically focus on technology, pedagogy, and course content" (p. 134) yet are also one-size-fits-all, and thus may not adequately address the unique requirements of individual instructors (Leary et al., 2020). This calls for a personalized online CPD that can considerably improve the quality of the training and therefore augment the level of benefit that instructor should obtain from such initiatives. An additional key consideration is the common challenge of possessing adequate digital skills to confidently navigate social media platforms (Donelan, 2016; Zhu et al., 2018), which can be a barrier that obstructs an optimal CPD-based learning journey. These considerations should be taken into account when formulating such training programs.

Another noteworthy aspect is that much of the existing literature is theoretical, highlighting the need for more in-depth individual case studies to provide a more realistic portrayal of practice (Acuyo, 2021), akin to our study, which examines the entire process both within and outside the WhatsApp platform. This approach would enable researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the complexities of social media-enabled participation in professional development initiatives (De Laat, 2012).

The aim of the study. To extract a replicable CPD-centric system that can be applied for similar purposes by charting the process of CPD-integrated e-training, examining meeting schedules, discussed topics, group dynamics, and interaction patterns.

Materials and Methods

To conduct the study, a descriptive multiple case research design was utilized to examine the CPD processes in two distinct WhatsApp groups: “MENA English Teachers Community” and “Secondary Teachers”, created by the British Embassy. The initiative initially involved grouping instructors for training in online seminars and workshops to adapt to the pandemic-affected environment. Invitations for CPD-focused seminars were sent via email, with a shift to a socially mediated WhatsApp platform by the end of 2023.

Two groups were selected for this study: the first is for all MENA teachers, while the second is exclusively for secondary English teachers. In essence, the former is

more general, and the latter is more specific. The primary objective of this study is to create a detailed “picture” of how this process unfolds, enabling future replication. Therefore, the comparison made between the groups is not to highlight contrasts but to fill in any gaps that might arise from analyzing just one e-group. Indeed, descriptive studies aim “to describe or explain relationships among phenomena, situations, and events as they occur,” as Thomlison (2001, p. 131) notes, aligning with the objectives of this scholarship. This study concentrates on two distinct case studies, qualifying it as a multiple case study. As Greene and David (1984, p. 75) explain, this approach is utilized “for generalizing to a target population of cases from the results of a purposefully selected sample of cases,” which, in our situation, involves two cases.

The Sample Population

Regarding the sample population, the first WhatsApp group “MENA English Teachers Community” comprises 990 users, each identified by a unique phone number. Consideration was given to those who were either added to the group or active in CPD-focused discussions. Consequently, 92 users were identified as participants. These individuals come from 17 different countries, with varying representation (Figure 1): Egypt (38.04%), Iraq (9.78%), Saudi Arabia (7.61%), Algeria (6.52%), Oman (6.52%), Libya (5.43%), Jordan (5.43%), Yemen (4.35%), United Arab Emirates (4.35%), Qatar (3.26%), Lebanon (2.17%), Morocco (2.17%), India (2.17%), Kuwait (2.17%), Tunisia (1.09%), Sri Lanka (1.09%), and Iran (1.09%).

Figure 1
The Countries’ Frequency of the Participants in Both WhatsApp Groups

Meanwhile, the second WhatsApp group “Secondary Teachers” consists of 780 users. Those accounted for in the study include members who were invited and added to the group or those who actively participated in online discussions. Within this specific timeframe, 77

participants were identified, originating from 17 countries. The breakdown is as follows (Figure 1): Egypt (41.57%), Iraq (10.11%), Oman (10.11%), Saudi Arabia (8.99%), Algeria (7.87%), Jordan (6.74%), Morocco (5.62%), Libya (5.62%), Yemen (4.49%),

United Arab Emirates (4.49%), Qatar (4.49%), India (3.37%), Lebanon (2.25%), Kuwait (2.25%), Iran (1.12%), Sri Lanka (1.12%), Tunisia (1.12%).

One noticeable trend in both populations is the significant presence of Egyptian participants, accounting for 38.05% in the first WhatsApp group and 41.57% in the second. This can be attributed to the fact that the entity monitoring the CPD program is the British Embassy of Egypt. Therefore, it is logical that the majority of instructors taking part in these CPD trainings are Egyptians. Another point worth emphasizing is that a small fraction of instructors do not belong to the MENA region. This is understandable, as invitations sent to invite instructors can be referred to other colleagues outside the immediate region.

Procedure

After extracting chat-transcript from both WhatsApp groups “MENA English Teachers Community” and “Secondary teachers” over a 40-days period (10th of January to 20th of February 2024), a meticulous protocol of cleaning the data was followed to enhance the analysis on a later stage. Initially, we removed irrelevant information including automated messages from WhatsApp, greetings, and notifications about members joining or leaving the group. This was done both semi-automatically meaning the process was partly manual and partly automated. It was also essential to organize the conversational threads in certain themes that would ease up the analysis process. Additionally, non-English content was translated for future use. Because regular meetings were held, Key Discussions were highlighted along with their respective dates that aligned with the analysis goals. This step-by-step procedure prepared the data for a comprehensive thematic analysis which is “a method for identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns of meaning (“themes”) within qualitative data” (Clarke & Braun, 2017, p. 297).

Data Collection Tools

This CPD-focused journey began with an email invitation to participate in a live ZOOM webinar during the COVID-19 crisis, which one of the researchers attended and received a certificate. In late 2023, an invitation from the British Embassy in Egypt was sent via email to join various WhatsApp groups, two of which were selected for an in-depth study using a descriptive multiple case study research design. To realize this research, participant observation was the initial data collection tool, as the researcher engaged in these groups and participated in WhatsApp-directed professional continuous development conversations. To thoroughly understand the dynamics of both WhatsApp groups, “Secondary Teachers”, and “MENA English Teachers Community”, recorded transcripts were extracted into a file for careful analysis. This digital trace data, as defined by Howison et al. (2011), is automatically stored by the social media platform and encompasses records of activity often through online information systems. Ohme et al. (2024) assert that it enables the analysis of content usage at an individual level and those methods and tools are available to make

content data accessible and analysable for social science scholars. The qualitative data from these e-groups permit a comprehensive mapping of how the CPD process is undertaken, identifying the interlinked elements that first, made this educational journey have such broad reach, and second, uncover the guidelines used to fulfil their mission.

Results

The results of the study revolve around three main elements namely the meeting schedules and topics, group dynamic and interaction in both WhatsApp groups and lastly, the overall process of CPD-infused WhatsApp-based e-training.

Meeting Schedules and Topics

The “Secondary Teachers” group appears to be targeted at educators operating with secondary-level students, discussing a wide variety of teaching techniques in this niche. During this 40-day period, they held about eight meetings, equating to two regular meetings per 10 days, to discuss a broad spectrum of topics ranging from social-emotional learning in education, developing speaking skills, role play strategy, teaching writing, to enhancing reading and writing skills. Conversely, the “MENA English Teachers Community” is more encompassing for English language teachers in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, sharing the same vision as the former. This vision is equipping educators with pertinent language teaching techniques, regardless of the educational level they operate in, be it primary, secondary, or tertiary. It is noteworthy to mention that, despite serving the same goal, the meeting format is different as this e-space is used more for announcing CPD-oriented seminars via Zoom, for instance. In these 40 days, only two post webinar meetings were held. Similar to the Secondary Teachers WhatsApp group, many interesting topics were tackled, including how to efficiently use technology in language teaching, teach grammar more creatively, and how to practically implement group activities. Two post-webinar meetings were held, and this group seems to group mainly MENA educators to inform them about upcoming events that may be of interest to them. So, it is another way to reach a broader audience the same way one can send an email reminder, one can send a text via WhatsApp.

Group Dynamic and Interaction

Because there were eight online CPD-focused meeting in the secondary teachers WhatsApp group, a noticeable level of interaction has been noticed but both groups displayed an active participation and a considerable level of engagement through sharing their ideas and experiences on the discussed topic whilst upholding the group rules.

An emphasis has been put on sharing their best practices and savoir-faire on the domain, which means not only they discuss the theory but also the practice as well as the various case scenarios to which this pedagogical concept apply. This can immensely enlarge and extend teachers’ repertoire of pedagogical methods and techniques.

Because the participants are from different countries, there was a context-bound layer that was added to these discussions because each member showcased their own perspective to the issue at hand. So, for many of the discussed elements, mani-fold culture-infused solutions were given which shows how enriching and enlightening the exchanges were.

The Process of CPD-Infused WhatsApp-Based E-Training

Both groups utilized direct messaging within WhatsApp among members, which can be regarded as an informal semi-structured online CPD session. In this setup, the moderator guided real-time discussions following specific prompts containing content-related instructions and ideas to be discussed by participants, employing various interactive modes. These included:

1. Polls: Used to gauge participants' understanding of a given concept or to survey the extent and manner in which a certain teaching method is employed in their respective classes. Instructors could use the responses to seek clarification, present problems, or share their thoughts on the subject matter.
2. Emojis: Moderately employed to express reactions as requested by the moderator. For example, members clicked 👍 to indicate agreement with a statement or to signal understanding of an instruction.

3. Videos: Moderators occasionally posted videos, prompting members to first view the pedagogical material, reflect on its content, and then share their opinions with others, fostering diversity and a multitude of perspectives.

4. Formal Online Webinars: These took place externally on platforms like Zoom, representing the other end of the spectrum from the informal WhatsApp External links are frequently shared in the groups, particularly the one catering to the MENA English teacher's community. These links invite users to participate in live formal webinars presented by professionals and teacher trainers. The aim is to refine instructors' skills, enabling them to deliver optimal learning experiences for their students.

Following the live sessions, recorded versions of the webinars are shared for those unable to attend. Additionally, post-webinar meetings are scheduled to discuss the webinar's content, sharing additional resources available on the official website of the British Embassy. This method effectively disseminates existing knowledge from the website to other e-platforms, maximizing outreach.

A CPD-oriented web-based practical system based on six elements, namely e-platforms, e-meetings, archiving, certification, website and the organization that orchestrates the whole process, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2
 CPD-Oriented Web-Based Practical System

One notable example is the provision of online free training courses (as seen in Figure 2), open to any educator looking to enhance their competencies at their own pace. Participants receive certification upon completing the e-training. Each session concludes with a call to action for teachers and a brief summary of the key elements discussed, ensuring that members retain crucial information from the meeting.

Overall, group admins supervise, organize, and moderate these online meetings by posting a variety of audio-visual materials, reminders, and follow-up messages. These efforts serve to encourage further participation and ensure fruitful exchanges, efficient communication, and resource-sharing during these instructive sessions.

Discussion

After meticulously tracing the CPD journey of teachers in both WhatsApp groups created by the British Embassy in Egypt – the organization overseeing the CPD initiative – and thoroughly reviewing their regular pedagogical activities in these online spaces, a scalable, intensive, cost-effective, and practical system was developed for future replication (Figure 2).

The organization oversees the entire CPD process across various spaces, continuously inviting potential members to join the WhatsApp groups primarily via email, resulting in an ever-growing population benefiting from these e-trainings. This scalability enables the system to train a massive number of instructors. Furthermore, the communication platforms, specifically WhatsApp groups in this case, serve as venues for conducting CPD meetings with different members in closed groups. These meetings can occur several times a month, in this instance, six times, highlighting their cost-effectiveness compared to regular face-to-face CPD workshops.

Additionally, the WhatsApp groups are utilized to post announcements regarding virtual seminars conducted on external platforms like Zoom. These platforms serve not only for seminar attendance but also for post-seminar discussions, where participants can share their thoughts and provide feedback about the CPD presentations. This aligns with Niess's (2011) findings, which emphasize that the success of CPD programs depends not solely on attendance but also on the post-PD support teachers receive. Within this community, professional relationships can be cultivated, and instructors can seek assistance when needed.

CPD-driven and social media-based systems have the potential to alleviate the burden of time and temporal limitations (Cook et al., 2017; Trust et al., 2016) that traditional CPD formats impose. By removing these constraints, online CPD-centric systems offer more intensive training to instructors, as research indicates that single-session workshops are unlikely to significantly improve teachers' practices (Darling-Hammond, 2017). Once a social media CPD-centered meeting takes place, it is automatically archived, allowing any member to review the content at any time or retrieve shared pedagogical materials. This digital repository facilitates revisiting past meetings, seeking help from other members, and evaluating CPD programs to potentially improve design and delivery (Nicolaidou & Petridou, 2011).

Active participants in these e-sessions can receive certificates, aiding in career advancement. Resource sharing is central to this CPD-focused exchange, with the official British Embassy website housing countless resources for instructors to utilize. Accredited courses are also available for participation. This CPD-focused ecosystem is optimized through the linkage of all these elements, multiplying training opportunities across all fronts.

One direct implication of this CPD system is its global reach. With such e-modes of CPD training, the audience continually increases, especially if a referral system is implemented where any member can add others,

maximizing the benefits of the system and significantly deepening their understanding and honing their skills in the target areas.

Another noteworthy implication is the cross-cultural exchange among instructors in these regular online meetings. Each member can present their unique perspective on a particular point, and the aggregation of these reflections can provide an all-encompassing picture of the discussed concept or demonstrate the various ways a technique can be deployed. This exchange can greatly expand instructors' horizons and enrich their teaching practices cross-culturally.

Conclusions

This research aims to outline the CPD journey by analyzing metrics such as materials used, frequency of virtual meetings, expansion of participant groups. Through this process, a blended, cost-effective, and scalable CPD system has been uncovered that has the potential to revolutionize this arena. This system can train instructors and educators globally on a regular basis, keeping them updated with the latest trends in (e)-education. Such optimization and maximization can significantly enhance both the teachers' teaching journey and the learners' educational endeavors.

With an automated archival system, all CPD-centered discussions can be traced and accessed by any member at any time. This allows for revisiting prior trainings and assessing stored multimedia-based data to improve the system overall. Moreover, these remote CPD trainings can be accredited, offering certificates to instructors each time they participate in these professional seminars, complemented by the wide spectrum of resources available on the official website of the organization.

Such a comprehensive CPD system holds the promise to upgrade teachers' skills worldwide and advance the teaching profession overall. This sustainable e-system can be leveraged by educators, stakeholders, and policy researchers seeking to replicate such models in their respective educational institutions. CPD for teachers will always remain at the forefront of their responsibilities and those of their stakeholders because their excellence lies in continuous growth and improvement.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki.

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ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Psychological Stress among University Students in Wartime: A Longitudinal Study

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

War has an extremely negative effect on people's psyches. This is especially true for student youth. They have to build personal lives and continue their studies in these difficult and traumatic conditions. The aim of the study: to identify the peculiarities of the dynamics of psychological trauma, and the manifestations of depression, anxiety and stress among students in wartime.

Material and Methods:

The study involved university students from Ukraine and European Union countries in 2022-2024. Respondents aged 20-50 years were divided into 4 groups. Group 1 consisted of 107 students, including 64 (59.8%) males and 43 (40.2%) females, living in areas where there was no hostilities or shelling (November 2022). Group 2 consisted of 103 students, including 52 (50.5%) males and 51 (49.5%) females, living in the area of active hostilities (November 2022). Group 3 consisted of 112 students, including 41 (36.6%) males and 71 (63.4%) females, living in areas where there was no hostilities or shelling (March 2024). Group 4 consisted of 115 students, including 30 (26.1%) males and 85 (73.9%) females, living in the area of active hostilities (March 2024). The study involved the development of the author's questionnaire and the adapted psychological test on the DASS-21, which is available on the Google Forms platform. The technique was found to have adequate internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha was 0.807.

Results:

Longitudinal studies have shown that university students in wartime are characterised by a tendency to increase psychogenics related to martial law, communication and safety. A closer look at the dynamics of psychopathological symptoms revealed a trend towards increased depression and anxiety, as well as a stabilisation of acute stress indicators in all groups. This indicates a serious deterioration in the mental health of the students and a further chronicisation of their neurotic disorders.

Conclusions:

The negative impact of the war in Ukraine on the mental health of student youth requires the active implementation of psychological support measures and psychoprophylaxis in accordance with individual psychodiagnostic findings.

Keywords:

mental health, psychotraumatic impact, anxiety, depression, stress, students, war

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Introduction

More than two years of war have changed the lives of Ukrainians. Living in difficult socioeconomic and psychological conditions of war leads to psychological trauma and mental health problems. Recent psychological studies have shown that the vast majority of the population (75.0%), including 92.5% of men and 57.5% of women, are in a state of moderate to severe stress during the full-scale war in Ukraine. The intensity of general stress for men and women does not differ significantly and is in the zone of marked tension (Kurova, 2022).

University students are no exception. Today's young people face new challenges: worrying about their own safety and the safety of others, studying under martial law (underground adapted premises, online learning, disruption of timetables and quality of teaching during rocket attacks), electricity, heating and water cuts, lack of internet and mobile communications, etc. Despite the inhumane conditions, some students continue to study and live in frontline areas. Other students try to stay away from the war. They live in places where there are no active hostilities. Current research shows that students' adaptation to stress in the context of prolonged war is characterised by a certain complexity, stages, duration, nature and purposefulness (Stadnik et al., 2022). This is why we believe that longitudinal studies need more attention. This allows us to identify certain features of the psychological dynamics of the personality of students in conditions of war and prolonged insecurity.

The aim of the study. To identify the peculiarities of the psycho-traumatic effects of the war in Ukraine on university students in 2022-2024, and to describe the dynamics of their depression, anxiety and stress to develop further psychological support and psychoprophylaxis.

Materials and Methods

Two phases of the study have been conducted: November 2022 (Phase 1) and March 2024 (Phase 2) during the war in Ukraine. The survey respondents were students from Ukraine and European Union countries. The respondents were aged between 20 and 50 years.

All respondents were divided into 4 groups.

Group 1 – students living in areas where there was no hostilities or shelling (the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine and EU countries) consisted of 107 people, including 64 (59.8%) males and 43 (40.2%) females (November 2022).

Group 2 – students living in the area of active hostilities (Kharkiv region, Ukraine) consisted of 103 people, including 52 (50.5%) males and 51 (49.5%) females (November 2022).

Group 3 – students living in areas where there was no hostilities or shelling (the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine and EU countries) consisted of 112 people, including 41 (36.6%) males and 71 (63.4%) females (March 2024).

Group 4 – students living in the area of active hostilities (Kharkiv region, Ukraine) consisted of 115 people, including 30 (26.1%) males and 85 (73.9%) females (March 2024).

Due to the war in Ukraine, the study was conducted by posting the author's questionnaire and the DASS-21 psychological test on the Google Forms platform for potential participants <https://forms.gle/1JXiLsLraBKnzAcW9>. In addition, all groups were monitored during remote and face-to-face teaching. Individual interviews were conducted when necessary.

To investigate the extent and nature of the psychological trauma experienced by university students in the context of war and martial law, we used a questionnaire developed in collaboration with the Scientific Research

Institute <https://forms.gle/sAaDRx4zcYF1inSz9>. KRPOCH
 The questionnaire is anonymous and consists of 14 questions relating to place of study, gender, age, region of residence and factors of psychological trauma in the war.

Data on stress levels and content were collected using the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21). The DASS-21 (21 items) is a short form of the DASS-42, a self-report scale designed to measure the negative emotional states of depression, anxiety and stress. The depression/anxiety/stress scales were scored according to the methodology (Henry & Crawford, 2005; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995). This technique is suitable for both clinical and nonclinical settings. For Ukrainian students, the Ukrainian version of the DASS-21 questionnaire was used (Melnyk & Stadnik, 2023). The number of students with normal, minor, moderate, severe or very severe manifestations was assessed. On the depression/anxiety/stress scales, the scores were as follows: normal manifestations (0-3/0-4/0-7 points),

minor manifestations (5-6/4-5/8-9 points), moderate manifestations (7-10/6-7/10-12 points), severe manifestations (11-13/8-9/13-16 points), and extremely severe manifestations (14+/10+/17+ points). The average score on the scales is calculated as an arithmetic mean.

SPSS 29.0.2 software was used for the statistical analysis. The data were analysed by means of descriptive statistics. The internal consistency was assessed by means of Cronbach's alpha.

Results

This research is part of a comprehensive study of mental health in the extreme conditions of martial law and full-scale war in Ukraine, which has been ongoing since February 2022.

The dynamics of the level and type of psychological trauma experienced by university students during the war are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1 shows the dynamics of the overall level of psychological trauma by groups of students in wartime.

Table 1

Dynamics of the Level and Type of Psychological Trauma of University Students in the Conditions of War in 2022-2024

Factors	Group 1, %			Group 2, %			Group 3, %			Group 4, %		
	Total	Male	Female									
Risk of personal safety	13.1	9.4	18.6	63.1	50.0	76.5	2.7	0.0	4.2	47.8	30.0	54.1
Fear of getting hurt	12.2	10.9	14.0	25.2	34.6	15.7	4.5	2.4	5.6	45.2	36.7	48.2
Risk of house losing	21.5	17.2	27.9	13.6	11.5	15.7	14.3	12.2	15.5	31.3	26.7	32.9
Risk of property losing	22.4	18.8	27.9	37.9	40.4	35.3	8.0	7.3	8.5	47.0	46.7	47.1
Having a job or other source of income	10.3	10.9	9.3	42.7	75.0	9.8	11.6	9.8	12.7	64.4	76.7	60.0
Fear of death	8.4	4.7	14.0	37.9	32.7	43.1	9.8	9.8	9.9	47.8	33.3	52.9
Risk of death of relatives, family	22.4	20.3	25.6	30.1	26.9	33.3	75.0	61.0	83.1	75.7	30.0	91.8
Separation from relatives, family	28.0	18.8	41.9	13.6	9.6	17.7	60.7	85.4	46.5	33.0	56.7	24.7
Problems in a new place of residence	42.1	43.8	39.5	17.5	23.1	11.8	31.3	29.3	32.4	12.2	20.0	9.4
Problems with communication with friends / loved ones	25.2	23.4	27.9	17.5	15.4	19.6	67.9	61.0	71.8	44.4	36.7	47.1
Coronavirus pandemic	5.6	4.7	7.0	4.9	3.9	5.9	5.4	4.9	5.6	6.1	3.3	7.1
Problems of communication with friends, relatives	8.4	7.8	9.3	7.8	9.6	5.9	25.0	22.0	26.8	34.8	36.7	34.1
Problems of romantic relationships	2.8	3.1	2.3	6.8	9.6	3.9	24.1	24.4	23.9	17.4	26.7	14.1
Problems associated with restricting martial law	8.4	9.4	7.0	15.5	17.3	13.7	73.2	87.8	64.8	59.1	56.7	60.0

Figure 1

Dynamics of the Total Level of Psychological Trauma by Groups of Students in Wartime in 2022-2024

Based on the results of the online survey, for Group 1 in 2022, the main factors of psychological trauma were problems adapting to a new place of residence (42.1%), separation from relatives and family (28.0%) and problems communicating with friends/relatives (25.2%). They were least concerned about romantic relationships (2.8%), the coronavirus pandemic (5.6%), fear of death (8.4%), problems communicating with friends/relatives (8.4%) and problems related to martial law (8.4%).

At the same time, in 2024 (Group 3), the following psychogenic factors came to the fore: risk of death of relatives/family (75.0%), problems related to martial law (73.2%), problems in communicating with friends/relatives (67.9%) and separation from relatives/family (60.7%). The following factors of psychological trauma had the lowest rates: risk of personal safety (2.7%), fear of injury (4.5%), and risk of loss of property (8.0%).

It should be noted that between 2022 and 2024, we recorded a more than threefold decrease in the following psychogenes: risk of personal safety, fear of injury and risk of property loss. This indicates that these problems are being addressed among this group of students. At the same time, there has been a sharp increase in problems with romantic relationships, problems related to martial law (more than eight times), problems communicating with friends/relatives and the risk of death of relatives/family (more than three times).

Gender-specific characteristics of students living in the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine and EU countries include a significant excess (two times) of psychogenic factors such as separation from relatives/family among males and personal safety risk among females.

For respondents in Group 2 in 2022, the most important vital indicators of psychological trauma were risk of personal safety (61.9%), lack of work or other sources

of income (37.1%), fear of death and risk of losing property (37.9%). This is due to difficult military and humanitarian situations (daily rocket attacks, frequent displacement, power, water and heat cuts).

At the same time, in 2024, the trends among Group 4 students changed slightly. The main psychogenes were the risk of death of relatives/family (75.7%), lack of work or other sources of income (64.4%) and problems related to martial law (59.1%). This can be explained by the further deterioration of the socio-psychological situation due to the prolongation of the war and the significant damage to civilian infrastructure. The coronavirus pandemic (6.1%) and problems at the new place of residence (12.2%) were the least common traumatic factors for students in Group 4.

It should be noted that in 2022-2024, we recorded a significant increase (more than three times) in the following psychogenes among university students in the Kharkiv region: problems with communication with friends/relatives, problems related to martial law, and problems in romantic relationships (more than twice). There has also been an increase in the following psychological traumas: risk of losing housing, risk of death of relatives and problems communicating with friends and family. In our view, this is due to unresolved mobilisation issues, frequent rocket and drone attacks on frontline areas, intensified enemy information and psychological operations, and the escalation of the situation on the frontline. At the same time, the risk to personal safety is reduced by 1/3. This can be explained by a certain adaptation of the students to the conditions of the frontline region during this period.

Gender peculiarities of students in the Kharkiv region in 2022-2024 include a significant excess (more than two times) of the following psychogenes among men: problems in romantic relationships, problems in a new place of residence, separation from relatives/family, and

for women – risk to personal safety, fear of death, risk of death of relatives/family. The symptoms of psychological trauma were further evaluated using the DASS-21.

The comparative characteristics of depression, anxiety and stress manifestations by respondent group in 2022-2024 are shown in Table 2-4.

Table 2
 Comparative Characteristics of Depression Manifestations by Respondent Group in 2022-2024

Depression manifestations	Group 1						Group 2					
	Total		Male		Female		Total		Male		Female	
	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%
Normal	93	86.9	58	90.6	35	81.4	81	78.6	44	84.6	37	72.5
Minor	7	6.5	3	4.7	4	9.3	10	9.7	4	7.7	6	11.8
Moderate	4	3.7	2	3.1	2	4.7	6	5.8	2	3.8	4	7.8
Severe	2	1.9	1	1.6	1	2.3	4	3.9	1	1.9	3	5.9
Extremely severe	1	0.9	0	0.0	1	2.3	2	1.9	1	1.9	1	2.0
Mean score	2.7		2.4		3.0		3.2		2.8		3.5	
-	Group 3						Group 4					
Normal	52	46.4	21	51.2	31	43.7	29	25.2	10	33.3	19	22.4
Minor	17	15.2	7	17.1	10	14.1	5	4.3	2	6.7	3	3.5
Moderate	27	24.1	8	19.5	19	26.8	46	40.0	11	36.7	35	41.2
Severe	11	9.8	3	7.3	8	11.3	24	20.9	5	16.7	19	22.4
Extremely severe	5	4.5	2	4.9	3	4.2	11	9.6	2	6.7	9	10.6
Mean score	5.1		4.7		5.3		7.2		6.3		7.5	

Table 3
 Comparative Characteristics of Anxiety Manifestations by Respondent Group in 2022-2024

Anxiety manifestations	Group 1						Group 2					
	Total		Male		Female		Total		Male		Female	
	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%
Normal	93	86.9	60	93.8	33	76.7	78	75.7	44	84.6	34	66.7
Minor	7	6.5	2	3.1	5	11.6	11	10.7	4	7.7	7	13.7
Moderate	4	3.7	1	1.6	3	7.0	7	6.8	2	3.8	5	9.8
Severe	2	1.9	1	1.6	1	2.3	4	3.9	1	1.9	3	5.9
Extremely severe	1	0.9	0	0.0	1	2.3	3	2.9	1	1.9	2	3.9
Mean score	2.5		2.2		2.8		3.0		2.6		3.3	
-	Group 3						Group 4					
Normal	59	52.7	23	56.1	36	50.7	40	34.8	14	46.7	31	36.5
Minor	16	14.3	6	14.6	10	14.1	23	20.0	6	20.0	17	20.0
Moderate	25	22.3	9	22.0	16	22.5	28	24.3	6	20.0	22	25.9
Severe	9	8.0	2	4.9	7	9.9	14	12.2	3	10.0	11	12.9
Extremely severe	3	2.7	1	2.4	2	2.8	10	8.7	1	3.3	4	4.7
Mean score	3.9		3.7		4.0		4.8		4.1		4.6	

Table 4
 Comparative Characteristics of Stress Manifestations by Respondent Group in 2022-2024

Stress manifestations	Group 1						Group 2					
	Total		Male		Female		Total		Male		Female	
	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%	people	%
Normal	92	86.0	52	81.3	40	93.0	80	77.7	37	71.2	43	84.3
Minor	9	8.4	7	10.9	2	4.7	12	11.7	8	15.4	4	7.8
Moderate	4	3.7	3	4.7	1	2.3	6	5.8	4	7.7	2	3.9
Severe	1	0.9	1	1.6	0	0.0	3	2.9	2	3.8	1	2.0
Extremely severe	1	0.9	1	1.6	0	0.0	2	1.9	1	1.9	1	2.0
Mean score	4.8		5.1		4.4		5.5		5.8		5.1	
-	Group 3						Group 4					
Normal	94	83.9	33	80.5	61	85.9	81	70.4	17	56.7	64	75.3
Minor	11	9.8	5	12.2	6	8.5	21	18.3	7	23.3	14	16.5
Moderate	5	4.5	1	2.4	4	5.6	8	7.0	4	13.3	4	4.7
Severe	1	0.9	1	2.4	0	0.0	3	2.6	1	3.3	2	2.4
Extremely severe	1	0.9	1	2.4	0	0.0	2	1.7	1	3.3	1	1.2
Mean score	4.9		5.2		4.7		5.7		6.7		5.4	

The dynamics of minor, moderate, severe and extremely severe depression manifestations among university students during the war are shown in Figure 2.

The dynamics of the Depression Scale revealed an almost 2-fold decrease in the absence of depressive symptoms among students in the Transcarpathian region and the EU in 2022-2024 (from 86.9% of students in Group 1 to 46.4% of students in Group 3). The scores

for minor (15.2%), moderate (24.1%), severe (9.8%) and extremely severe (9.8%) manifestations of depression among Group 3 students in 2024 increased more than 2-fold. This indicates a serious deterioration in their mental health. This was usually manifested by complaints of frequent headaches, stomach pain, rapid heartbeats or breathing, sweating, dizziness and unexplained panic.

Figure 2

Dynamics of Depression Manifestations among University Students in Wartime in 2022-2024

The gender specificity of students is that depression is more pronounced among women in Group 3 than among all groups of students studying in the Transcarpathian region and in the EU. The scores of moderate (26.8%), severe (11.3%) and extremely severe (4.2%) manifestations of depression among women in 2024 increased more than 2-fold compared to the same data in 2022 (4.7%, 2.3% and 2.3% respectively) and more than that among men in Group 3 (19.5% and 7.3% respectively).

The dynamics of the Depression Scale among students in the Kharkiv region (Groups 2 and 4) were revealed as follows. Over the period 2022-2024, there was a decrease (more than 3-fold) in the absence of depressive symptoms from 78.6% (students in Group 2) to 22.4% (students in Group 4). The scores for moderate (40.0%), severe (20.9) and extremely severe (9.6%) manifestations of depression among students in Group 4 in 2024 increased more than 5-fold. These scores are the highest of all the groups studied. This indicates a significant deterioration in the mental health of students in the Kharkiv region in 2022-2024.

The gender differences in depression manifestations among students in the Kharkiv region are the greatest among women in Group 4 (2024). This suggests that these women have significant mental health problems. In 2024, the percentages of women with moderate (26.7%), severe (11.3%), and extremely severe (4.2%) depression increased more than 2-fold compared to those in 2022 (4.7%, 2.3% and 2.3% respectively). Men in Group 4 had lower levels of depression than women did. Minor (6.7%), moderate (36.7%), severe (16.7%)

and extremely severe (6.7%) manifestations of depression were less common among men in Group 4 than among women (3.5%, 41.2%, 22.4% and 10.6% respectively).

The dynamics of minor, moderate, severe and extremely severe anxiety manifestations among university students during the war are shown in Figure 3.

We analysed the dynamics of the Anxiety Scale score based on a study of students using the DASS-21. Among students living in the Transcarpathian region and the EU in 2022, 86.9% had no anxiety symptoms (normal manifestations), 6.5% had minor symptoms, 3.7% had moderate symptoms, 1.9% had severe symptoms, and 0.9% had critical anxiety. In 2024, 52.7% of the students had no anxiety symptoms (normal manifestations), 14.3% had minor symptoms, 3.7% had moderate symptoms, 8.0% had severe symptoms, and 2.7% had extremely severe anxiety. The increase in particularly severe and extremely severe manifestations of anxiety among students indicates a sharp deterioration in their psychological state, the presence of neurotic disorders and maladjustment in the third year of the war.

It should be noted that, according to the results of the 2022 gender survey, anxiety is more pronounced among women. Minor anxiety symptoms were observed in 11.6% of women, moderate in 7.0%, severe and extremely severe in 2.3%, these percentages were significantly greater than those for men (3.1%, 1.6%, 1.6% and 0.0%, respectively). In 2024, there is no statistically significant difference between the anxiety scores of women and men in the Transcarpathian region and the EU.

Figure 3
 Dynamics of Anxiety Manifestations among University Students in Wartime in 2022-2024

The dynamics of the Anxiety Scale among students in the Kharkiv region showed that moderate (24.4%), severe (12.2%) and extremely severe (8.7%) manifestations of anxiety among students in Group 4 in 2024 increased more than 3 times and were the highest among all study groups. This indicates a significant deterioration in the mental health of the students, manifested by complaints of palpitations, pain behind the breastbone, rapid breathing, excessive sweating, trembling, weakness, fatigue, dizziness, frequent urination and sleep problems. Among all gender groups in the Kharkiv region, anxiety is most pronounced among women in Group 4 (2024),

indicating significant mental disorders among these respondents.

The scores of moderate (25.9%), severe (12.9%) and extremely severe (4.7%) anxiety among women in 2024 increased by 1.5-2 times compared to those in 2022 (9.8%, 5.9% and 3.9% respectively).

The anxiety scores of the men in Group 4 (20.0%, 10.0% and 3.3%, respectively) were also lower than those of the women.

The dynamics of minor, moderate, severe and extremely severe stress manifestations among university students during the war are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4
 Dynamics of Stress Manifestations among University Students in Wartime in 2022-2024

The dynamics of the Stress Scale among students in the Transcarpathian region and the EU (Groups 1 and 3) are as follows. In 2022, 8.4% of the students experienced

minor manifestations of stress; 1.7% experienced moderate manifestations; 0.9% of the students in Group 1 had severe and extremely severe manifestations. In

2024, 9.8% of students experienced minor manifestations of stress; 4.5% experienced moderate manifestations; 0.9% of the students in Group 3 experienced severe or extremely severe manifestations. The lack of dynamics indicates a certain stabilisation of acute stress among students in the Transcarpathian region and the EU during the war.

The gender peculiarities of stress manifestations among students in the Transcarpathian region and the EU are that moderate, severe and extremely severe manifestations were observed in 2.4% of the students, which is greater than the same percentages among women (5.6%, 0.0% and 0.0%, respectively). This indicates that male students are less able to adapt to stress.

By analysing the dynamics of the Stress Scale among students in the Kharkiv region (Group 2 and Group 4), we noted a slight increase in minor (18.3%) and moderate (7.0%) manifestations of stress in 2024. At the same time, the scores of severe and extremely severe

stress among students in the Kharkiv region remained virtually unchanged in 2022-2024, indicating an insufficient level of adaptation to stress among students in the third year of the war.

Gender differences among students studying in the Kharkiv region are that among all gender groups, stress is most pronounced among males in Group 4 (2024). This indicates significant psychological disturbance in these respondents, manifested by heart palpitations, breathing difficulties and insomnia. Male students were more likely to have diarrhoea (or, conversely, constipation), acute respiratory diseases, skin diseases (neurodermatitis), allergies, tremors and sticky hands. The scores of men with minor (23.3%), moderate (13.3%), severe (3.3%) and extremely severe (3.3%) stress in 2024 are significantly greater than those of women (16.5%, 4.7%, 2.4% and 1.2% respectively).

The dynamics of the total manifestations of depression, anxiety and stress among university students during the war are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5

Dynamics of Total Manifestations of Depression, Anxiety and Stress among University Students in Wartime

During the 2022-2024 war in Ukraine, we observed the following changes in the psychological well-being of university students.

The average scores on the Depression Scale for students in Groups 1 and 2 (2022) were 2.7 and 3.2 points respectively, which are more than twice as high as those for students in Group 3 (5.1 points) and Group 4 (7.2 points) in 2024. This upwards trend in depression indicates a certain tendency toward chronic neurotic disorders among university students against the background of the protracted war in Ukraine, which manifests itself in increased complaints of low mood, low self-esteem, pessimism, apathy, lethargy, fatigue, constant dissatisfaction and hopelessness. In terms of gender differences in the Depression Scale, the average score of female students was greater than that of male students in all study groups.

We also see an upwards trend on the Anxiety Scale. The average scores for students in Group 3 and Group 4 in 2024 were 3.9 and 4.8 points, respectively, which are

significantly greater than those in 2022 for Group 1 (2.5 points) and Group 2 (3.0 points). We believe this is due to the continued uncertainty of the military and humanitarian situation in Ukraine as a result of the war. This took the form of increased helplessness, insecurity, powerlessness, powerlessness, insecurity, loneliness, a sense of failure and an inability to make decisions. It should be noted that the average score on the Anxiety Scale for female students was greater than that for male students in all study groups.

The average scores on the Stress Scale for students in Groups 1 and 3 living in the Transcarpathian region and the EU remained virtually unchanged over the period 2022-2024 (4.8 and 4.9 points respectively) and were lower than those for students in Groups 2 and 4 living in the Kharkiv region (5.5 and 5.7 points respectively). This indicates a much worse military and humanitarian situation in the Kharkiv region, which is close to the front line, as well as a certain adaptation of students to acute psychogenic conditions in the context of the 2022-2024

war. It should be noted that the average score of the male students on the Stress Scale was greater than that of the female students in all study groups.

Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated for each of the three scales of the DASS-21 as an estimate of internal consistency reliability. Acceptable levels of reliability were found for all scales: Depression scale $\alpha=0.712$, Anxiety scale $\alpha=0.783$, Stress scale $\alpha=0.733$. Cronbach's alpha for the total scale was $\alpha=0.807$. These scores are an indication of the homogeneity of the items in each dimension of the scale.

Discussion

Since the end of the Second World War, Europe has not seen a war of scale and intensity that is currently taking place in Ukraine. This war has affected the lives of more than 40 million Ukrainians, including hundreds of thousands of students.

Most students continue their studies at university. Some students (a small number, mostly women) have been forced to become refugees and continue their studies remotely in EU countries. It must be borne in mind that in the globalised modern world, the effects of a war in one country will inevitably have repercussions in other countries. War affects international politics, economics, population migration, health care, etc., to varying degrees.

This study is an integral part of a longitudinal study that includes a comprehensive examination of the mental health of Ukrainian students continuing their studies under extreme conditions: low-intensity war (2014-2022), the COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2022), and martial law and full-scale war in Ukraine (from 2022 to the present). This study explored stressors that may affect the academic performance and well-being of young people in a military environment. Such risk factors include mental, emotional and behavioural problems.

For a specific study, the dynamics of depression, anxiety and stress indicators were examined among students at state universities in Ukraine who studied in 2022-2024 in significantly different regions. The study also included students who continued their studies at a distance in EU countries. This choice was necessitated by the need to study the effects of warfare on students under different conditions of stress: Group 1 (students living in areas where there was no hostilities or shelling, Transcarpathian region of Ukraine and EU countries, November 2022); Group 2 (students living in the area of active hostilities, Kharkiv region, Ukraine, November 2022); Group 3 (students living in areas where there was no hostilities or shelling, Transcarpathian region of Ukraine and EU countries, March 2024); and Group 4 (students living in the area of active hostilities, Kharkiv region, Ukraine, March 2024).

Recent scientific publications in the social and behavioural sciences, as well as the authors' own experience, allowed us to build the methodological basis for our research.

Previous studies have examined the effects of extreme conditions of low-intensity warfare on military personnel (Melnyk et al., 2019). The level of resistance of soldiers

to combat psychological trauma depends on the impact of extreme conditions (participation in combat operations). Even with a low level of exposure to extreme conditions (lack of combat experience), there is a high probability of mental disorders, a tendency toward personality disorders, and behavioural and activity disorders.

The COVID-19 pandemic has added extreme conditions to the existing conditions of low-intensity warfare in our study of the mental health of military personnel and students. These new conditions made it possible to determine that military men with combat experience were significantly less likely to suffer from anxiety, depression, stress and sleep disorders than military men without such experience (Melnyk et al., 2020; Melnyk & Stadnik, 2020). We assumed that the mental health of students in low-intensity wars and under extreme pandemic conditions would be significantly different from the mental health of trained military personnel. Therefore, we only looked at students who were involved in sports. Most students had a moderate level of mental health, approximately one-third had a high level of mental health, and less than 10.0% had a low level of mental health (Melnyk et al., 2022). Similar findings of the positive impact of physical activity and sport on respondents' mental health during this period have been reported by other researchers (Lange et al., 2023; Watson et al., 2023). These studies confirm that systematic physical activity has a positive effect on mental health, even in the extreme conditions of a pandemic and/or low-intensity war. The positive effect of physical activity on students' mental health has been demonstrated in numerous studies (Mahindru et al., 2023; Melnyk, 2019; Yao et al., 2023), including under the extreme conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic (Huang et al., 2023; Precht et al., 2023).

Studies of student youth in a full-scale war show that the greatest psychogenics are: risk of death of relatives, family separation from relatives, family, lack of work or other source of income, fear of death and risk of loss of property (Stadnik et al., 2022).

There is also a link between psychological distress and chronic fatigue and sleep problems. This relationship is bidirectional, as symptoms can be both a source and a consequence of psychological distress. In addition, the dependence of the mental state of the students on the degree of their physical proximity to the combat zone was revealed. The negative impact on students' mental health increases with proximity to the combat zone (Stadnik et al., 2023). The analysis of the psychological well-being of university students and their choice of coping strategies to overcome life crises in the context of the war in Ukraine shows that the level of negative impact was greater the closer the students were to the zone of active hostilities. University students use different coping strategies in stressful war situations in Ukraine. However, the coping strategy of cognitive restructuring is more commonly used. Coping strategies of social support and self-criticism are typical for students living in the area of active military operations (Pypenko et al., 2023).

Personal resources that might support the resilience of a sample of Ukrainian students to the stress of war were explored. Emotional stability and resilience were found to be the resources most strongly associated with fewer posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms and fewer physical complaints, while benevolence and integrity also played a role (Kokun & Bezverkhyi, 2024).

The problems of Ukrainian refugee students pursuing higher education in Europe have been studied by Pentón Herrera and Byndas (2023), and Regnoli et al. (2023). Refugees have been found to experience psychological stress that can lead to mental health problems. War-related population movements have a negative impact on mental health, which is regularly confirmed by numerous studies (Fino et al., 2020; Radhouane, 2023).

The unprecedented scale of Russian aggression against Ukraine has caused the largest mass displacement of people in modern history (Patel & Erickson, 2022). Studies show that asylum seekers and refugees are particularly vulnerable to traumatic experiences that are threefold in nature: pre-migration, peri-migration, and post-migration (Chen et al., 2017). According to researchers (Marchi et al., 2022), the experience of war and displacement can have profound effects on children's affective development and mental health. However, the mechanisms underlying these effects remain unknown.

In addition, refugees are exposed to war through the media coverage of war-related violence. This leads to stress and overstimulation (Chudzicka-Czupala et al., 2023).

The relevance of certain psychological symptoms (anxiety, depression, insomnia, and poor health) among civilians and especially young people during war is widely recognised (Baroud & Dirani, 2023; Zaid et al., 2023).

Contemporary research during the Russian-Ukrainian War has shown high prevalence rates of symptoms of psychological distress, anxiety, depression and insomnia among Ukrainians aged 18 and over. In addition, researchers stress the need for further research and the need to develop effective survival strategies for Ukrainians during the war (Długosz, 2023; Khraban, 2022; Pavlova & Rogowska, 2023).

The choice of the subject of research and techniques was determined by the real needs and problems identified in the scientific literature. The Depression Anxiety Stress Scales are widely used in modern research as a reliable screening tool for studying the impact of war on individuals' mental health (Çelebi & Durmuş Sarikahya, 2023; Chudzicka-Czupala et al., 2023; El-Ghitany et al., 2024).

The application of this technique made it possible to identify psychogenic factors affecting students in war and martial law conditions, as well as to detail psychopathological symptoms according to the Anxiety, Depression and Stress Scales.

We analysed the data from the DASS-21 study and compared it with other research techniques, namely, the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-28), and the Social Support Questionnaire (F-SozU K-22), in the context of dividing students into groups according to the level of

influence of their proximity to the combat zone. Similar results have been found in a number of studies: manifestations of depression were more common in women than in men. At the same time, severe and extremely severe manifestations of anxiety (2-3 times higher than similar indicators in respondents) were observed among students who were not in the vicinity of the combat zone (Stadnik et al., 2022; 2023). There was evidence of a strong dose-response relationship between war-related stressors and meeting criteria for posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and complex PTSD (CPTSD). Participants who had the highest exposure to war-related stressors were significantly more likely to meet the requirements for PTSD (OR=4.20; 95% CI=2.96-5.95) and CPTSD (OR=8.12; 95% CI=5.11-12.91) compared to the least exposed (Karatzias et al., 2023).

Similar trends, albeit at slightly different rates, have been reported by other researchers. People living in a war-torn region of Ukraine also had a significantly increased risk of PTSD (OR=4.11, 95% CI=2.37-7.13), severe anxiety (OR=3.10, 95% CI=1.83-5.27), and moderate/severe depression (OR=2.65, 95% CI=1.79-3.92) (Osokina et al., 2023).

Thus, the use of different techniques to study this problem shows similar results – the war had a significant negative impact on the mental state of students, and the closer they were to the war zone, the greater the impact.

In line with previous research on the impact of the Russian-Ukrainian War on the mental health of students' youth in Ukraine, predictors are described that determine the impact of features of interpersonal style on the index of perceived stress, index of coping resources, positive attitude towards others, autonomy, environmental management, personal development, life goals, self-perception, psychological well-being, inclusion, control, risk acceptance, and resilience (Lunov et al., 2023). Effects can also be characterised as stages of mental health impact: acute reactions – acute disorder – chronic stress/disorder at both personal and societal levels (Vus & Esterlis, 2022). Gilreath et al. (2022) studied stressors that can affect the academic performance and well-being of youth during wartime.

This study has several limitations. First, it should be noted that the study was conducted under active war conditions, which may have contributed to the high scores. Second, our study is limited by the small number of participants in each group. It was not possible to carry out a more comprehensive assessment of the students under these conditions.

It must be considered that the participants were young students. This may have influenced the results. Some researchers argue that young people are more interested in contemporary social dilemmas than other age groups, and that this affects their mental health and psychological well-being (Barchielli et al. 2022; Bezzi 2022; Galliano 2020).

It should also be noted that in the study of Ukrainian students, we used only the Ukrainian versions of the author's questionnaire and the DASS-21 questionnaire (Melnyk & Stadnik, 2023). This approach avoided any

possible misinterpretation of the questions and optimised the response time.

Nevertheless, this has provided important information that provides an insight into the mental health status of the sample and allows conclusions to be drawn about the dynamics of this process over the last two years, which can help to take early action to improve the mental health status of students.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the ongoing war in Ukraine has had a negative impact on the mental health of university students.

Our longitudinal studies conducted in 2022-2024 showed that university students in the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine and EU countries are characterised by a significant decrease (by 3 to 4 times) in the following psychogenes: risk of personal safety, fear of injury, and risk of property loss. This indicates a reduction in their role in the psychological trauma of students. At the same time, there was a significant increase in problems with romantic relationships, problems related to martial law (8 times), problems communicating with friends/relatives and the risk of death of relatives/family (3 times).

Among university students who did not change their place of permanent residence and stayed in the frontline area of the Kharkiv region in 2022-2024, we recorded a significant increase in the following psychogenes: problems communicating with friends/relatives, problems related to martial law, problems in romantic relationships (more than 3 times), the risk of losing housing, the risk of death of relatives, and problems communicating with friends/relatives (more than 2 times). In our opinion, this is due to the problems of mobilisation, frequent rocket and drone attacks on the frontline areas, the intensification of the enemy's information and psychological operations and the escalation of the situation on the frontline. At the same time, there is a decrease in the risk to personal safety (by 1/3), which can be explained by a certain adaptation of the students to the conditions of the frontline region during this period.

Gender dynamics are characterised by a significant prevalence of psychogenic factors such as separation from relatives and family (Groups 1 and 3) and problems with romantic relationships and new residences (Groups 2 and 4). For women, the greatest risks are personal safety (in the Transcarpathian region and the EU), fear of death, and the risk of death for relatives and family (in the Kharkiv region).

A more detailed study of the dynamics of psychopathological symptoms, carried out using the DASS-21 technique, showed that in 2022-2024 among students in the Transcarpathian region and the EU, the scores of minor, moderate, severe and extremely severe manifestations of depression increased more than 2-fold. Among students living in the Kharkiv region, it increased more than 5-fold and was the highest of all student groups. This indicates a serious deterioration in students' mental health and is usually manifested by frequent headaches, stomach aches, rapid heartbeat or breathing,

sweating, dizziness and occasional panic. The gender peculiarity of depression is its prevalence among women in all groups, with the highest levels of depression among women in Group 4 (Kharkiv region) in 2024.

The studied dynamics of anxiety among students showed an increase in moderate, severe and extremely severe manifestations of anxiety both among students in Group 3 (the Transcarpathian region and the EU) and among students in Group 4 (the Kharkiv region). At the same time, the anxiety scores of Group 4 students increased more than 3-fold in 2024 and were the highest of the all groups. The symptoms included palpitations, pain behind the breastbone, rapid breathing, excessive sweating, trembling, weakness, fatigue, dizziness, and frequent urination and sleep problems. Gender peculiarities: the anxiety scores of women and men in the Transcarpathian region and the EU are not significantly different, and among all gender groups, anxiety is most pronounced among women in Group 4 in 2024.

The recorded dynamics of stress among university students during the war showed a certain stabilisation and the absence of acute stress among students in the Transcarpathian region and the EU, as well as an increase in minor and moderate stress among students in the Kharkiv region. Symptoms included palpitations, difficulty breathing, insomnia, frequent diarrhoea (or, conversely, constipation), acute respiratory problems, skin problems (neurodermatitis), allergies, tremors and sticky hands. The gender specificity of stress manifestations among students is the prevalence of stress among males in all groups studied. In 2024, men in Group 4 (Kharkiv region) had the highest level of stress, indicating that these respondents had acute mental disorders.

The dynamics of general depression, anxiety and stress scores among university students during the war showed a trend towards an increase in depression and anxiety and a stabilisation of stress scores. This indicates the chronicity of neurotic disorders among students in the context of the protracted war in Ukraine. Symptoms included increasing complaints of low mood, low self-esteem, pessimism, apathy, lethargy, fatigue, constant dissatisfaction and hopelessness.

In our view, the prospect of further research lies in the development of effective measures of psychological support and psychoprophylaxis among students.

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Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki, as reflected in prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee. Permission for this research was received from the Research Committee of Virtue and Ethics Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (protocol no. 023-3/SRIKRPOCH dated 10.08.2023). Informed consent was sought from all the participants.

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**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES**

Health Care Sciences

**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL
SCIENCES**

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Digitalisation Factors Influencing the Dynamic Capabilities of Small and Medium Enterprises in the Healthcare Sector

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

Digitalization is problematized as one of the ways to improve dynamic capabilities of healthcare sector small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in their strive to stay competitive in today's digital society. Digitalisation and dynamic capability are current key issues in both academia and practice due to the recent advances in information and communication technologies. Nonetheless, there is inadequate research informing what and why digitalisation can be leveraged to enhance the dynamic capabilities (DC), in the context of SMEs in healthcare sector. The aim of the study: to explore and explain factors influencing DC of healthcare SMEs in South Africa.

Material and Methods:

The study employed task-technology fit theory as a lens to explain digitalisation factors influencing the DC of SMEs. To achieve the aim of the study, a deductive approach was followed. The study population was healthcare sector SMEs, in South Africa. The sampling frame was 384 randomly selected SMEs, in a self-administered survey.

Results:

The empirical results show that SME performance ($\beta=0.132, p<0.05$), task-technology fit ($\beta=0.052, p<0.05$), internet access ($\beta=0.235, p<0.05$), customer service ($\beta=0.057, p<0.05$), information sharing ($\beta=0.022, p<0.05$), innovation ($\beta=0.125, p<0.05$), and data security ($\beta=0.427, p<0.05$) are highly significant in the digitalisation of DC of SMEs. While cost saving ($\beta=0.178, p>0.05$) was found to be less significant.

Conclusions:

The study has explained and shown that appropriating technology to task during digitalisation is key to enhancing dynamic capabilities, in the context of South African healthcare sector SMEs. The cost of digital technology is a none factor. Subsequently, digitalization is a people-driven transformation journey.

Keywords:

digitalisation, dynamic capabilities, task-technology fit, small and medium enterprises, healthcare sector, South Africa.

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Introduction

In the epoch of digital technologies (DTs), both academics and practitioners have strongly been advocating for the value of achieving dynamic capabilities (e.g., Ozanne et al., 2022). Along the same lines, a plethora of research (e.g., Bolosha et al., 2022; Fatoki, 2021; Gaglio et al., 2022; Matekenya & Moyo, 2022; Rashidirad & Salimian, 2020) posit that achieving dynamic capabilities requires an inclusive digital strategy. This paper argues that there is a need to enhance the dynamic capabilities (DC) of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to contribute to economic expansion (Khurana et al., 2022; Matarazzo et al., 2021; Suhendi et al., 2020). As emphasized by Farida and Setiawan (2022); Weaven et al. (2021), it is substantial that SMEs in developing nations enhance the DC to attain a competitive edge (Owoseni & Twinomurinzi, 2019) and to compete with multinational enterprises in the emerging digital world (Achieng & Malatji, 2022; Suhendi et al., 2020).

Baloyi and Khanyile (2020) alluded that the substantial role of SMEs as the lubricants of economic expansion in South Africa has largely been recognized. Sibiyi et al. (2023) and Tshwete (2020) have shown the substantial role of SMEs in eliminating poverty, creating job opportunities (Mashavira et al., 2022) and enhancing economic expansion (Loury-Okoumba & Mafini, 2021; Masocha, 2019; van Staden, 2022). Several government agencies in South Africa such as the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), SEDA, the Department of Small Business Development (DSBD), the National Empowerment Fund (NEF), and the Small Enterprise Finance Agency (SEFA) prioritize support for SMEs (Kelly et al., 2021). According to Sibiyi et al. (2023), the number of registered SMEs in South Africa during the first quarter of 2021 was projected to be close to 2.3 million (SEDA, 2021). Baloyi and Khanyile (2020) state that SMEs play a substantial role in the economy as they make up 95.0% of businesses, which contributes 60.0% to job creation (Venter & Hayidakis, 2021) and around 45.0–50.0% of South Africa's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Loury-Okoumba & Mafini, 2021; Mashavira et al., 2022; Matekenya & Moyo, 2022). Furthermore, a report by the National Planning Commission (2020) has documented that SMEs in South Africa will create 90.0% of new job opportunities by 2030 (Kelly et al., 2021; Matekenya & Moyo, 2022). Nonetheless, many scholars (e.g., Mhlongo & Daya, 2023; Sibiyi et al., 2023) have identified a plethora of challenges preventing the expansion of SMEs in South Africa.

A growing body of literature on SME growth has shown that a lack of digital technologies (Bvuma & Marnewick, 2020), poor infrastructure (Loury-Okoumba & Mafini, 2021; Sibiyi et al., 2023) and limited access to technology (Kademeteme & Twinomurinzi, 2019), are the major reasons that prevent SMEs from enhancing their DC (Hermawati & Gunawan, 2019). Extant research (e.g., Mashal & Morrish, 2023; Raimo et al., 2023) suggest that SMEs may resort to digitalisation to tackle their challenges to enhance the DC (Khurana et al., 2022). Digitalisation

has become popular among SMEs, particularly in the healthcare sector (Mashal & Morrish, 2023; Raimo et al., 2023). In support of the above viewpoint, a report published by Deloitte UK's Centre for Health Solution (2020) state that about 65.0% of SMEs in the healthcare sector have increased the adoption of DT (Mashal & Morrish, 2023; Raimo et al., 2023). Recent scholarly work by Moretti et al. (2023) defines digitalization as the process of converting information into digital format.

In a broader context, a plethora of research (Moretti et al., 2023) refers to digitalisation as the process of combining DTs into everyday life (Warner & Wäger, 2019), business processes and enterprises (Achieng & Malatji, 2022). Recent scholarly works found that digitalisation can enable SMEs in the healthcare sector to improve health services (Raimo et al., 2023), reduce cost (Moretti et al., 2023), reduce health inequalities (Saifudin et al., 2021), gain access to electronic health records (Spanò et al., 2023), provide services to patients (Cerchione et al., 2023) and allow healthcare providers to monitor patient's vital signs (Balta et al., 2021). A growing body of literature on DTs (Khurana et al., 2022; Moretti et al., 2023) has shown that digitalisation can enhance SMEs' DC (Raimo et al., 2023; Warner & Wäger, 2019). In the emerging digital world and with the scarcity of resources (Moretti et al., 2023), budget constraints (Sumaili et al., 2018), and limited opportunities to directly influence the market structure (Schoemaker et al., 2018), DC is an important set of capabilities that SMEs should have because it will enable them to quickly detect market changes before rivals do (Engelmann, 2024).

Engelmann (2024) states that the development of DC among SMEs relies on sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring (Khan et al., 2021). Firstly, sensing capabilities explain the evaluation of opportunities that are available in the market (Engelmann, 2024); with DTs helping SMEs to sense as they can identify opportunities such as discovering and collaborating with patients on the internet (Spanò et al., 2023). Secondly, seizing capabilities entails enterprises' reaction to market requirements to reduce cost (Engelmann, 2024; Khan et al., 2021). DTs can help SMEs in the healthcare sector seize the opportunity of doing business on the Internet at a lower cost (Raimo et al., 2023; Suhendi et al., 2020; Warner & Wäger, 2019). Lastly, reconfiguring capabilities is the development of new enterprises' capabilities to support new business models (Engelmann, 2024).

Scholarly literature on DC (e.g., Khurana et al., 2022; Zamani et al., 2022) state that the development of business models among enterprises is integral to creating sustainable growth (Engelmann, 2024; Khan et al., 2021). Along the same lines, empirical studies conducted on DC (Engelmann, 2024; Warner & Wäger, 2019) have argued that SMEs must develop new business models to provide services to customers (Zamani et al., 2022). DTs can enable SMEs in the Healthcare sector to provide services to their patients on

the internet (North et al., 2020; Raimo et al., 2023; Spanò et al., 2023).

The aim of the study. To explore and explain digitalisation factors influencing the DC of SMEs in the healthcare sector.

To realize the aim, the research question was formulated as what are the digitalisation factors influencing the DC of SMEs in the healthcare sector?

Materials and Methods

As the aim of this present study was to explore and explain digitalisation factors influencing the DC of SMEs in the healthcare sector, a deductive research approach was followed. A sampling frame was acquired through the South African Small Enterprise Development Agency (SEDA). According to a survey undertaken by SEDA (2021), the number of registered SMEs, including those in the healthcare sector, in the Gauteng province of South Africa during the first quarter of 2021 was 786,027. The study sample size was, therefore 384. This sample size is in line with Krejcie and Morgan (1970) who stated that a population that is between 75,000 and 1,000,000 is well represented by a sample size of 384.

The present study was cross-sectional in nature since data collection only occurred at one specific point in time. A self-administered survey questionnaire was employed to obtain data from the SMEs operating in Gauteng province. A total of 500 survey questionnaires were sent to 500 SMEs operating in the Healthcare sector. Of the 500 questionnaires, only 300 were returned. This meant a response rate of 60.0%, which is

considered to be a good return (Salah & Ayyash, 2023). The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 28. A reliability test was also conducted in this present study. Scholarly work by Hall et al. (2023) states that the prime reason for conducting a reliability test is to examine the level of consistency of the survey questionnaire. A plethora of research (e.g., Dzomonda & Fatoki, 2019; Martinez-Corona et al., 2020) has indicated that a questionnaire is considered reliable if Cronbach's alpha (CA) is greater or equal to 0.7 (Cheung et al., 2023; Ogujiuba et al., 2023). As documented in Table 1, Cronbach's alpha was determined to be 0.886, which is considered excellent, since it exceeded the recommended value of 0.7.

Table 1
Reliability Result of the Data Collection Instrument

Reliability results		
Cronbach's alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items	Number of items
0.886	0.886	78

The present study was designed as a cross-sectional study envisioned obtaining data from five hundred (500) SMEs operating in the Healthcare sector. Three hundred (300) responded accordingly. Table 2 presents the demographical statistics of respondents. The demographic variables include gender, age (years), education, job position, sector, use of DTs, and types of DTs used.

Table 2
Demographical Statistics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency		
	Person	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Gender	Male	187	63.3
	Female	113	37.7
	Total	300	100.0
Age (years)	20 – 30	222	74.0
	41 – 50	64	21.3
	Above 50	14	4.7
	Total	300	100.0
Education	Matric	20	6.7
	Diploma	46	15.3
	B-tech	170	56.7
	Master's	58	19.3
	PhD	6	2.0
Total	300	100.0	
Job position	SME manager	300	100.0
	Total	300	100.0
Sector	Healthcare	300	100.0
	Total	300	100.0
Use of DTs	Yes	264	88.0
	No	36	12.0
	Total	300	100.0
Types of DTs used	Facebook	64	21.3
	WhatsApp	222	74.0
	X (Twitter)	14	4.7
	Total	300	100.0

As shown in Table 63.3% (187) of participants representing healthcare SMEs were males, whilst 37.7% (113) were females. Furthermore, the findings in Table 2 reveal that 74.0% (222) of participants were between the ages of 20 to 30, 21.3% (64) were between 41 to 50 and 4.7% (14) were above 50 years. Regarding education, 56.7% (170) of participants had a B-tech, followed by 19.3% (58) who had a master's, 15.3% (46) had a diploma, 6.7% (20) had a matric and only 2.0% (6) had a PhD. Concerning job position, Table 2 shows that 100% (300) of participants were SMEs managers. Moreover, the results in Table 2 show that 100.0% (300) of SMEs operate in the healthcare sector. Concerning the use of digital technologies (DT), 88.0% (264) of participants revealed that they are using DTs, whilst 12.0% (36) alluded that they are not using DTs.

Furthermore, Table 2 shows that 74.0% (222) of participants use WhatsApp, 21.3% (64) use Facebook, and 4.7% (14) use X (formerly Twitter).

Regression Analysis

At this stage, regression analysis was utilised to evaluate the degree to which INO, FPM CSE, SHI, DST, IEA, COS, and TTF influence the digitalisation of SMEs to improve the DC of SMEs in the Healthcare sector. As shown in Table 3, the regression findings show a significant value of 0.000, implying that the regression model can be used for the digitisation of SMEs to improve the DC. In this present study, the predictor variable accounts for 68.1% of the variance in the digitalisation of SMEs in the healthcare sector to improve the DC and the adjusted R Square (R^2) equals=0.681.

Table 3
 Regression Statistics*

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.117	0.021	-	0.052	0.000	-	-
INO	0.125	0.195	0.248	0.125	0.022	0.154	2.453
FPM	0.132	0.183	0.256	1.144	0.000	0.178	1.027
CSE	0.057	0.172	0.174	0.182	0.014	0.352	3.117
SHI	0.022	0.126	0.143	3.122	0.003	0.221	1.120
DST	0.427	0.272	0.177	0.172	0.000	0.248	2.026
IEA	0.235	0.175	0.247	1.665	0.032	0.332	2.049
COS	0.178	0.195	-0.423	0.186	0.687	0.172	1.125
TTF	0.052	0.218	0.200	1.208	0.002	0.118	2.110

Note. *Dependent variable – Digitalisation of SMEs to improve the DC; INO – innovation; FPM – firm performance; CSE – customer service; SHI – sharing information; DST – data security; IEA – internet access; COS – cost savings; TTF – task-technology fit.

As displayed in Table 3, the results show that INO ($\beta=0.125, p<0.05$), FPM ($\beta=0.132, p<0.05$), and CSE ($\beta=0.057, p<0.05$) hypotheses positively influence the digitalisation of SMEs to improve the DC. Along the same lines, this present study confirmed that SHI ($\beta=0.022, p<0.05$) and DST ($\beta=0.427, p<0.05$) have a positive effect on the digitisation of SMEs to improve the DC. Furthermore, the study proved that IEA ($\beta=0.235, p<0.05$) and TTF ($\beta=0.052, p<0.05$) hypotheses positively influence the digitalisation of SMEs to improve the DC. However, this present study

found that one factor has a negative influence on the digitalisation of SMEs to improve the DC, namely, COS ($\beta=0.178, p>0.05$).

The results demonstrated in Table 4 indicate that seven (7) hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, H6, and H8) are supported, whilst H7 is not supported. To check if there is an existence of multi-collinearity, this present study employed the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). As depicted in Table 3, all the VIF numbers were below 5, which implies that there is no existence of multi-collinearity.

Table 4
 Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Constructs	Std. Beta (β)	p-values	Decision
H1	INO	0.125	0.022*	Supported
H2	FPM	0.132	0.000*	Supported
H3	CSE	0.057	0.014*	Supported
H4	SHI	0.022	0.003*	Supported
H5	DST	0.427	0.000*	Supported
H6	IEA	0.235	0.032*	Supported
H7	COS	0.178	0.687**	Not supported
H8	TTF	0.052	0.013*	Supported

Note. * $p<0.05$; ** $p<0.01$; INO – innovation; FPM – firm performance; CSE – customer service; SHI – sharing information; DST – data security; IEA – internet access; COS – cost savings; TTF – task-technology fit.

Results and Discussion

The model (Figure 1) shows factors that are significant to digitalization with respect to improving dynamic capabilities of South African healthcare sector SMEs.

Task Characteristics

As shown in Table 4, INO ($p=0.022<0.05$) has a positive effect on the digitalisation of SMEs to improve the DC. This outcome is consistent with Raghavan et al. (2021), who stated that DTs such as Cloud Computing can help SMEs in the Healthcare sector become innovative by sharing information and communicating with patients on the internet (Arega & Sharma, 2023). Also, the present study proved that FPM ($p=0.000<0.05$) has a positive effect on the digitalisation of SMEs. This result is in line with Vishwakarma et al. (2023), who stated that

DTs, for example, artificial intelligence (AI) can enable SMEs in the healthcare sector to refine patient treatment, enhance firm performance (Gautam et al., 2022), and improve the DC (Drydakis, 2022). The positive effect of CSE ($p=0.014<0.05$) on the digitalisation of SMEs is also confirmed. In support of this result, several scholars (Cerchione et al., 2023; Spanò et al., 2023) state that DT can enable SMEs in the healthcare sector to improve customer service (Vishwakarma et al., 2023). Similarly, the present study proved that SHI ($p=0.003<0.05$) has a positive effect on the digitalisation of SMEs. This result is in line with Spanò et al., (2023) who alluded that DTs can enable SMEs in the healthcare sector to share information with patients (Engelmann, 2024).

Figure 1

A Model for Digitalisation Factors Influencing the Dynamic Capabilities of SMEs in Healthcare Sector

Technology Characteristics

As shown in Table 4, DST ($p=0.000<0.05$) has a positive effect on the digitalisation of SMEs. This result is supported by Benzidia et al. (2021), who found that DTs can enable SMEs in the healthcare sector to protect the data of patients by implementing security measures (Raghavan et al., 2021). The positive effect of IEA ($p=0.014<0.05$) on the digitalisation of SMEs is also confirmed. As emphasized by Spanò et al. (2023) and Vishwakarma et al. (2023) DTs enable SMEs in the healthcare sector to collaborate with their patients on the Internet (Arega & Sharma, 2023). However, the present study found that COS ($p=0.687>0.05$) has a negative effect on the digitalisation of SMEs. This result is in line with Khurana et al. (2022), who found that DTs are not easy to adopt, because SMEs take time to replace old technologies with new ones.

Task-Technology Fit

On the other hand, the present study found that TTF ($p=0.013<0.05$) has a positive effect on the digitalisation of SMEs. In support of this result, Wang et al. (2019)

state that TTF plays a substantial role in the use of Big Data Analytics (BDA) in mobile cloud healthcare system. And by the same token, this paper has shown that TTF is an appropriate theoretical lens to help explain digitalization and dynamic capability in the healthcare sector SMEs.

Conclusions

In this paper, digitalization was problematized as one of the ways to improve dynamic capabilities of healthcare sector Small and Medium Enterprises in their strive to stay competitive in today's digital society. This paper has explained and shown that appropriating technology to task during digitalization is key to enhancing dynamic capabilities, in the context of South African healthcare sector SMEs. The cost of digital technology is a none factor influencing the digitalization process. Subsequently, digitalisation is a people-driven transformation journey. The paper argues that customer service, innovation, SME performance, and sharing of information play a positive role on the digitalisation

journey of SMEs. Access to Internet, task-technology fit, and data security are also significant factors. On the other hand, saving costs plays a negative role in the digitalisation process. This paper concludes that digitalisation accompanied by good infrastructure, financing, and unlimited access to technology is key to improving dynamic capabilities of healthcare sector SMEs.

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Ethical Approval

The study obtained ethical clearance from the institution's Ethics Committee (Ref NO. FCRE/ICT/2022/03/001 (1)).

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ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Conceptualizing a Model for the Use of Software as a Service to Improve the Dynamic Capabilities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Healthcare Sector

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

To remain competitive in today's digital society, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the healthcare sector need to consider effective ways to improve their dynamic capabilities (DCs) using Software as a Service (SaaS). SaaS and DCs are current key issues in both academia and practice. The aim of the study: to develop the conceptual model for the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs in South Africa.

Material and Methods:

The study employed Task-Technology Fit (TTF) and Fit Viability Model (FVM) as a lens to develop a model for the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs. To achieve the aim of the study, a deductive approach was followed. The study population was healthcare SMEs, in South Africa. The sampling frame was 384 randomly selected SMEs, in a self-administered survey.

Results:

The study results show that customer service ($\beta=0.125$, $p<0.05$), sharing information ($\beta=0.132$, $p<0.05$), internet access ($\beta=0.057$, $p<0.05$), data security ($\beta=0.022$, $p<0.05$), top management support ($\beta=0.427$, $p<0.05$), competitive pressure ($\beta=0.178$, $p<0.05$), viability ($\beta=0.325$, $p<0.05$) and task-technology fit ($\beta=0.032$, $p<0.05$) are highly significant on the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs. While finance ($\beta=0.235$, $p>0.05$) and infrastructure ($\beta=0.052$, $p>0.05$) were found to be less significant.

Conclusions:

The conceptual model was developed to identify and explain the factors influencing the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare enterprises. This model is based on TTF, FVM and external constructs (organisational and environmental characteristics) that are key to improving the DC of South African healthcare SMEs.

Keywords:

dynamic capabilities, fit viability model, software as a service, small and medium enterprises, healthcare sector, South Africa

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Introduction

In recent years, healthcare Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have become an essential instrument for individuals in many countries across the globe (Fahmi et al., 2022; Raimo et al., 2023; Salisu et al., 2021). Additionally, healthcare sector SMEs improve the economy by providing services to patients, eradicating poverty, and generating new job opportunities (Balta et al., 2021; Moretti et al., 2023). Nonetheless, several scholars (Enesi & Ibrahim, 2021; Salisu et al., 2021) reported that the advent of COVID-19 caused significant harm to various enterprises across the globe. In support of this viewpoint, empirical studies conducted globally reported that 60% of SMEs face the challenge of liquidation and about 50% have stopped operating because of the lockdown measures (Bularafa & Adamu, 2021; Trawnih et al., 2021).

According to a plethora of research (Bularafa & Adamu, 2021; Khurana et al., 2022), while the COVID-19 pandemic impacted various sectors, the healthcare SMEs have witnessed a severe impact due to their lack of technological resources. Consequently, healthcare sector SMEs must use technology to enhance their performance and survive in the face of exogenous shocks (Preko & Boateng, 2020; Zimmermann et al., 2022). In recent years, enterprises' use of Cloud services and digital products (Pypenko, 2019) has become widespread (Aceto et al., 2020; Moyo & Loock, 2021; Suhendi et al., 2020). The Internet enables healthcare organisations to communicate with patients anytime and anywhere (Deloitte UK's Centre for Health Solution, 2020; Raimo et al., 2023). One of those Cloud services is Software as a Service (SaaS) (Majengo & Mbise, 2022; Mokwena & Hlebel, 2018; Moyo & Loock, 2021). A plethora of scholarly literature elucidates that SaaS is viewed as a tool for facilitating communication mechanisms and drawing people together through sharing content (Allassafi, 2021; Loukis et al., 2019). Extant research refers to SaaS as a Cloud service model that enables various sectors to rent information and communication technology (ICT) services from a Cloud Service Provider (CSP) on the Internet (Khaki & Khan, 2023; Majengo & Mbise, 2022; Suhendi et al., 2020).

Within the various sectors, SaaS has taken a substantial role in healthcare SMEs (Deloitte UK's Centre for Health Solution, 2020; Moyo & Loock, 2021; Raimo et al., 2023). Recent scholarly literature indicates that the use of digital technologies (DTs) such as SaaS enables the healthcare SMEs to improve healthcare services, reduce costs, and have access to electronic health records (Meri et al., 2019; Moretti et al., 2023; Moyo & Loock, 2021; Raimo et al., 2023; Suhendi et al., 2020). Additionally, several scholars (Moyo & Loock, 2021; Raimo et al., 2023) posit that DTs such as tele-health, electronic communications, web and Cloud-based services, if implemented in a targeted manner, have the potential to minimize health inequalities and improve people's lives through a substantial change in the way in which healthcare services are provided to patients (Balta et al., 2021; Moretti et al., 2023; Spanò et al., 2023). Furthermore, other scholars posit that Cloud services

can contribute to SMEs' dynamic capabilities (Engelmann, 2024; Khurana et al., 2022; Moyo & Loock, 2021; Suhendi et al., 2020). According to recent scholarly literature (Drydakis, 2022; Khurana et al., 2022), DCs are substantial because they enable SMEs to quickly detect market changes before their rivals do (Warner & Wäger, 2019). Extant research found that in the SME sector, the development of DCs relies on sensing, seizing and reconfiguring (Khurana et al., 2022; Engelmann, 2024). From a business perspective, sensing focuses on discovering opportunities, seizing aims to utilize the opportunities, and reconfiguring improve business models (Drydakis, 2022). With the help of SaaS, healthcare sector SMEs can sense the opportunity to collaborate with patients on the Internet (Suhendi et al., 2020; Spanò et al., 2023). Furthermore, SaaS can enable healthcare sector SMEs to seize the opportunity of doing business on the Internet (Johnston et al., 2023). Moreover, SaaS can help healthcare sector SMEs to transform by reconfiguring their business models (Engelmann, 2024; Majengo & Mbise, 2022).

In the epoch of the digital economy, web and Cloud-based services may be tools to promote innovation and enhance enterprises' performance (Moyo & Loock, 2021; Suhendi et al., 2020). Empirical studies conducted globally (Deloitte UK's Centre for Health Solution, 2020; Nicolau et al., 2022; Raimo et al., 2023; Statista, 2023) affirm that the use of web and Cloud-based services (SaaS) can help healthcare organisations to improve the way in which they provide healthcare services to patients (Balta et al., 2021; Moretti et al., 2023; Spanò et al., 2023). Yet, within South Africa, there are limited studies on the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.

The aim of the study. To develop the conceptual model for the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.

The following study model was conceptualised from by triangulating the two theoretical models that were used as lenses for this study. The two theoretical models underpinned by this study included Task-Technology Fit (TTF) and Fit Viability Model (FVM). The study hypotheses (H1–H10) are shown in Figure 1.

Materials and Methods

To explain DCs and the use of SaaS by healthcare sector SMEs, positivism was identified as the most suitable paradigm for the study. A plethora of research (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Hall et al., 2022; Hasan, 2016) pointed out that positivist studies are associated with quantitative research approach that test hypotheses. The present study utilized a survey questionnaire to collect data. The survey questionnaire used a five Likert scale method with anchors starting from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Healthcare SMEs that had used SaaS form the population of this study. A survey conducted by Small Enterprise Development Agency (SEDA, 2021) reported that the registered number of SMEs in South Africa during the first quarter of 2021 was projected to be close to 786,027.

Figure 1
 Conceptualized Study Model for the Use of SaaS to Improve the DCs of Healthcare SMEs

Note.

- H1: Customer service influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H2: Sharing information influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H3: Internet access influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H4: Data security influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H5: Top management support influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H6: Finance influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H7: Competitive pressure influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H8: Infrastructure influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H9: Viability influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.
- H10: Task-Technology Fit influences the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs.

Scholarly work undertaken by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) noted that a population that is between 75,000 and 1,000,000 is represented by a sample size of 384. As a result, the sample size of this present study was 384. To evade non-respondent issues when collecting data. The research team distributed 500 questionnaires to healthcare sector SMEs. A 60.0% response rate was attained from these questionnaires, with the participants answering 300 of the questionnaires. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 28.

Reliability Analysis

In this stage, a reliability test was conducted. Recent scholarly works (Hair et al., 2019; Hall et al., 2022; Salah & Ayyash, 2023) point out that the principal reason for performing a reliability test is to examine the level of consistency of the questionnaire. Additionally, scholarly work by Hall et al. (2022) posit that the questionnaire is considered reliable if Cronbach's alpha

meets a value of more than 0.7. As shown in Table 1, Cronbach's alpha meet the threshold requirements.

Table 1
 Reliability Result of the Data Collection Instrument

Reliability results		
Cronbach's alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items	Number of items
0.886	0.886	78

Healthcare SMEs in South Africa were the target respondents. The study envisioned to obtain data from five hundred (500) SMEs. Three hundred 300 responded accordingly.

Table 2 presents the demographical statistics of respondents. The demographic variables include gender, age (years), education and use of SaaS.

Table 2
Demographical Statistics of Respondents

Variables		Frequency		
		Person	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Gender	Male	187	63.3	63.3
	Female	113	37.7	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	-
Age (years)	20 – 30	222	74.0	74.0
	41 – 50	64	21.3	95.3
	Above 50	14	4.7	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	-
Education	Matric	20	6.7	6.7
	Diploma	46	15.3	22.0
	B-tech	170	56.7	78.7
	Master's	58	19.3	98.0
	PhD	6	2.0	100.0
Total	300	100.0	-	
Use of Saas	Yes	264	88.0	88.0
	No	36	12.0	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	-

As shown in Table 2, 63.3% (187) of participants representing healthcare SMEs were males, whilst 37.7% (113) were females. Furthermore, the findings in Table 2 reveal that 74.0% (222) of participants were between the ages of 20 to 30, 21.3% (64) were between 41 to 50 and 4.7% (14) were above 50 years.

Regarding education, 56.7% (170) of participants had a B-tech, followed by 19.3% (58) who had a master's, 15.3% (46) had a diploma, 6.7% (20) had a matric and only 2.0% (6) had a PhD.

Concerning the use of SaaS, 88.0% (264) of participants revealed that they are using SaaS, whilst 12.0% (36) alluded that they are not using SaaS.

Measurement Model Analysis

Before assessing the structural model, measurement model analysis was conducted. A plethora of research (Khan et al., 2021; Kikawa et al., 2022; Maroufkhani et al., 2020; Steenkamp & Maydeu-Olivares, 2023; Yusoff et al., 2020) point out that measurement model analysis is performed by using factor loadings (FL), composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). As recommended by Hair et al. (2019) for the measurement model test results to be acceptable, FL and CR must meet a value of more than 0.7 and AVE a value of more than 0.5. As displayed in Table 3, all the FL, CR, and AVE values meet the threshold requirements.

Table 3
Loadings Reliability and Validity Statistics

Constructs	Number of items	Factor loadings	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted
CUS	3	0.788–0.920	0.721	0.742
SHI	3	0.645–0.747	0.903	0.682
IEA	3	0.726–0.888	0.836	0.667
DAS	3	0.673–0.934	0.903	0.755
TMS	3	0.709–0.854	0.907	0.762
FIC	3	0.738–0.834	0.894	0.681
CMP	3	0.683–0.809	0.894	0.689
IFT	3	0.685–0.925	0.904	0.664
VAB	3	0.826–0.920	0.758	0.685
TTF	3	0.826–0.880	0.825	0.725

Note. CUS – customer service; SHI – sharing information; IEA – internet access; DAS – data security; TMS – top management support; FIC – finance; CMP – competitive pressure; IFT – infrastructure; VAB – viability; TTF – task-technology fit.

Assessment of Structural Model

In this stage, structural equation modelling (SEM) was utilised. According to recent scholarly literature (Al-Mamary, 2022; Kikawa et al., 2022; Steenkamp & Maydeu-Olivares, 2023), SEM is used in research studies to test the hypotheses.

As displayed in Table 4, the SEM results show that the hypotheses CUS ($\beta=0.125, p<0.05$), SHI ($\beta=0.132,$

$p<0.05$), IEA ($\beta=0.057, p<0.05$), DAS ($\beta=0.022, p<0.05$), TMS ($\beta=0.427, p<0.05$), CMP ($\beta=0.178, p<0.05$), VAB ($\beta=0.325, p<0.05$) and TTF ($\beta=0.032, p<0.05$) have a positive effect on the use of SaaS. Whilst the hypotheses FIC ($\beta=0.235, p>0.05$) and IFT ($\beta=0.052, p>0.05$) have a negative effect on the use of SaaS.

Table 4
Hypotheses Testing

No	Constructs	Std. Beta (β)	p-values	Decision
H1	CUS	0.125	0.022*	Supported
H2	SHI	0.132	0.000*	Supported
H3	IEA	0.057	0.014*	Supported
H4	DAS	0.022	0.003*	Supported
H5	TMS	0.427	0.000*	Supported
H6	FIC	0.235	0.732*	Not Supported
H7	CMP	0.178	0.002**	Supported
H8	IFT	0.052	0.853*	Not Supported
H9	VAB	0.325	0.012*	Supported
H10	TTF	0.032	0.000*	Supported

Note. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; CUS – customer service; SHI – sharing information; IEA – internet access; DAS – data security; TMS – top management support; FIC – finance; CMP – competitive pressure; IFT – infrastructure; VAB – viability; TTF – task-technology fit.

As displayed in Table 4 and Figure 2, eight hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, H7, H9, and H10) were supported because they have a p-value of less than < 0.05 , while

two hypotheses (H6 and H8) were not supported because they have a p-value of greater than > 0.05 .

Figure 2
A Model for the Use of SaaS to Improve the Dynamic Capabilities of South African Healthcare sector SMEs

Results and Discussion

The model (Figure 2) shows the factors that are significant to the use of SaaS to improve the dynamic capabilities (DCs) of South African healthcare SMEs.

Task Characteristics

The study results in Table 4 show that CUS ($p=0.022 < 0.05$) has a positive effect on the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare sector SMEs.

Therefore, H1 is supported. This outcome is in line with Raimo et al. (2023) who found that web and Cloud-services helped healthcare organisations in Italy to improve customer service. In addition, the present study proved that SHI ($p=0.000<0.05$) has positive effect on the use of SaaS. Therefore, H2 is supported. In support of this outcome, a plethora of research (Mokwena & Hlebela, 2018; Moyo & Looek, 2021; Raimo et al., 2023) point out that SaaS can help healthcare sector SMEs to share information with their patients.

Technology Characteristics

As displayed in Table 4, IEA ($p=0.014<0.05$) has a positive effect on the use of SaaS. Therefore, H3 is supported. Recent scholarly works (Johnston et al., 2023; Khaki & Khan, 2023; Raimo et al., 2023) have shown that having access to the internet can help organisations, particularly healthcare sector SMEs to improve the DCs (Hercheui & Ranjith, 2020; Pietronudo et al., 2022; Suhendi et al., 2020; Weaven et al., 2021). Similarly, the positive effect of DAS ($p=0.003<0.05$) on the use of SaaS is confirmed. Therefore, H4 is supported. This outcome is supported by Ganiga et al. (2018) and Mubarakali et al. (2020) who pointed out that Cloud services can help healthcare organisations to manage and protect the data of patients.

Organisational Characteristics

As displayed in Table 4, TMS ($p=0.000<0.05$) has a positive effect on the use of SaaS. Therefore, H5 is supported. This outcome is consistent with Nassoura (2020) who found that top management support (TMS) play a substantial role on the adoption of Cloud Computing in Jordanian healthcare organisations. However, the present study found that FIC ($p=0.732>0.05$) has a negative influence on the use of SaaS. Therefore, H6 is not supported. This outcome is consistent with Khurana et al. (2022) who argued that digital technologies (DTs) are not easy to adopt, because the majority of SMEs lack funding.

Environmental Characteristics

On the other hand, the present study found that CMP ($p=0.000<0.05$) has a positive effect on the use of SaaS. Therefore, H7 is supported. This outcome is in line with Raimo et al. (2023) who found that healthcare organisations use Cloud-services in reaction to the increase in competitive pressure (CMP) which is fueled by the danger of losing customers.

However, the study found that IFT ($p=0.853>0.05$) has a negative effect on the use of SaaS. Therefore, H8 is not supported. Recent scholarly works (Bolosha et al., 2022; Bvuma & Marnewick, 2020) reported that about 70.0-80.0% of SMEs in South Africa collapse because of inadequate infrastructure.

Viability

As displayed in Table 4, VAB ($p=0.012<0.05$) has a positive effect on the use of SaaS among healthcare SMEs. Therefore, H9 is supported.

This outcome is consistent with Liang et al. (2021) who found that viability play a substantial role in the adoption of Blockchain Technology among healthcare organisations.

Task-Technology Fit

The positive effect of TTF ($p=0.000<0.05$) on the use of SaaS is also confirmed. Therefore, H10 is supported. This outcome in line with Wang et al. (2019) who found that TTF play a substantial role in the use of Big Data Analytics (BDA) mobile cloud healthcare system.

Conclusions

In this paper, the conceptual model is proposed to identify and explain the factors influencing the use of Software as a Service (SaaS) to improve the dynamic capabilities (DCs) of healthcare SMEs. This model is based on Task-Technology Fit (TTF) and Fit Viability Model (FVM) and some external constructs (organisational characteristics and environment characteristics). The study results show that customer service (CSE), sharing information (SHI), internet access (IEA), data security (DAS), top management support (TMS), competitive pressure (CMP), viability (VAB) and task-technology fit (TTF) play a positive role on the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs. However, the present study also found that finance (FIC) and infrastructure (IFT) play a negative role on the use of SaaS to improve the DCs of healthcare SMEs. This paper concludes that SaaS is key to improving DCs of healthcare sector SMEs.

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Ethical Approval

The study obtained ethical clearance from the institution's Ethics Committee (Ref NO. FCRE/ICT/2022/03/001 (1)).

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Choosing to Die with the Help or by the Hand of a Doctor (Medically-Assisted Death): Limitations and Safety Profiles

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

Depression severity can be profoundly impacting the life of individuals, while its persistence can provoke the conviction that recovery is unattainable. One of the extreme consequences is the request for euthanasia. However, during major depression cognition can be significantly impaired. In this study, we comment on the exemplar case of a Belgian lady, Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer, who made that request and obtained the desired outcome.

The aim of the study: to consider a specific case of a patient with major depressive disorder and the role of doctors in informing the decision about medically assisted death.

Material and Methods:

The history of the request made by Mrs. Godelieva is described. The procedure was followed by the reactive initiatives of the son of the lady, who made a formal complaint against the procedure that brought his mother to death and appealed the European Court of Justice.

Results:

A description of what happened is briefly reported, including considerations on the clinical treatments received by Mrs. Godelieva, the roles interpreted by the doctors she consulted and, finally, the appropriateness of the decision taken.

Conclusions:

In revisiting this case, the decision-making process during major depression episodes and the authenticity and robustness of end-of-life choices in similar cases are critically examined. Comments are made on the frequency of cognitive impairments during major depressive episodes and the need to provide depressed people the necessary support during their important choices.

Keywords:

Major depression, chronic persistent depression, euthanasia, medically assisted suicide, care for depressed people, psychological support, European Court of Justice

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Introduction

Depression and Bio-Legal Issues: General Framework
Depression is a clinical reality frequently encountered in psychogeriatric clinics; it is the leading cause of

disability globally, as confirmed by the Global Burden of Disease study (GBD) which calculated, for 2019, the disability adjusted life years (sum of years of life lost in

the world due to premature mortality and years of life lived in conditions of suboptimal health) estimated at 46.9 million years (GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators, 2020). Following the statistical indicators provided by the World Health Organization (WHO), there would be over 300 million depressed people in the world (World Health Organization, 2022) with a prevalence that can affect one in five people in the general population, increasing with age; 31.74% of old people (65+ years of age) would, in fact, be affected by a depressive disorder and its prevalence would be higher (40.8%) in developing countries (Zenebe et al., 2021), with peaks recorded in Africa – 43.1% (Bedaso et al., 2022) and in India – 34.4% (Pilania et al., 2019). In nursing homes, 18.9% of older adults reportedly suffer from major depressive disorder (MDD), as indicated by a recent meta-analysis of 32 observational studies (Fornaro et al., 2020).

Also in Italy, depression is the most widespread mental disorder: about 5-6% of the population is affected by it, while 10-15% of it would have experienced a depressive episode at least once in life even if these indicators vary according to the sources and diagnostic methodologies used. Recent studies indicate that MDD could affect over 7.5 million people (11.4% of the population), mainly women with low schooling and poor economic status (de Girolamo et al., 2005).

Not only because of its frequency, depression raises many (complex) practical questions, including juridical ones (as in the case of patient suicide) (Cupelli, 2013) and, more generally, bioethical ones, often faced with a feeble voice by psychiatrists “whose opinion is only rarely sought but, above all, even more rarely expressed” (Bersani et al., 2020, p. 57). It is therefore necessary to reflect on the impact of depression and the possible impact of cognitive impairment, especially in cases of severe (major) depression, when important decisions are to be taken by the individual affected by it. This is what we are meant to do in this short essay, in which we propose to address the quality and robustness of end-of-life choices given the relationship that exists, especially in old age, among depression, cognitive decline and risk of progression from mild cognitive impairment (MCI) to frank dementia (Rosenberg et al., 2013).

We would do so starting from a public matter that has recently come under examination by the European Court of Human Rights (Judgment n. 78017 of 4 October 2022, *Mortier vs. Belgique*), immediately acknowledging that the regulatory framework which Belgium has adopted for the non-punishability of euthanasia is very liberal (Cembrani et al., 2014; Dentamaro, 2019): it also allows minors capable of discernment and people affected by a mental pathology who find themselves “in a useless condition of physical or psychological suffering, unbearable and incurable” to access it if adults (Mehlum et al., 2020) provided they are capable of understanding and wanting, with limitations that have however proved to be completely insufficient in the face of the exponential growth of cases. In this regard, the latest Report from the Commission Fédérale de Contrôle et D'évaluation de L'euthanasie (2023) – documents the

progressive increase in cases of euthanasia (from 259 in 2003 to 2,790 in 2021) to which people mainly over 70 years old resorted (in 67.1% of cases), and those mostly affected by a neoplastic pathology (63.4% of cases), mainly through administration of barbiturates (99.6% of cases). Very small, but present, mental and behavioral disorders: this happened in 94 cases in 2021 (1.9% of the total); in 45 cases (equal to 0.9% of the total) this occurred due to a personality disorder, a depressive picture and schizophrenia; in 49 cases (1.0% of the total) due to the existence of a cognitive disorder produced by Alzheimer's disease, vascular dementia or Lewy bodies' dementia. In most patients, different types of suffering, both physical and psychic, were present simultaneously. The suffering has been described as constant, unbearable, and unrelievable. Among the most often mentioned physical sufferings are air hunger, digestive obstruction with vomiting, constant pain. Among the most frequent causes of psychological suffering, are dependence on others, loss of dignity, loneliness, social isolation and despair.

In this article we would like to try to give an answer to the many problematic questions that the principle of self-determination raises in the event that the holder of the right is a particularly fragile, vulnerable, influenced or otherwise suggestible person, and what is the support that these people must be guaranteed by whoever has the responsibility of care, especially in situations where the good put at risk is the protection of life protected by the European Convention on Human Rights (Council of Europe, 2002).

The aim of the study. To consider the exemplary case of a Belgian lady, Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer, with a major depressive disorder and the role of doctors in informing the decision about medically assisted death.

Materials and Methods

The Death through Euthanasia of Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer, which Came before the Examination of the European Court of Justice Following the Complaint Presented by Her Son

At the material time, Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer was a 64-year-old Belgian woman, suffering for over 40 years from a depressive disorder generally considered as “major” and unresponsive to the pharmacological treatments prescribed by the numerous psychiatrists near whom she was in therapy. She herself had decided to die by resorting to euthanasia, a practice permitted in that country due to the effects of the law of 28 May 2002, then modified by the law of 28 February 2014, which extended this option to minors with the consent of parents or legal representatives without setting any age limit, however, as instead requested by the Dutch legislation. Dr. G. T., her general practitioner, was informed of the decision, but declined the woman's invitation to start the procedure. He advised her to contact Prof. W. D., a Belgian oncologist well known in his country for being a strong supporter of euthanasia.

According to the reconstruction of the events made by the judges of Strasbourg, on 29 September 2011 Prof. W. D. spoke to Mrs. de Troyer, learning that she was at that time

being followed by a psychiatrist, that her depressive disorder had started very early (at the age of 19 years) and that the many pharmacological approaches had never resulted in full recovery, even if there was a break in 2006 when the woman, after the suicide of her husband, had embarked on a new relationship, then abruptly interrupted.

For the last two years, Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer had decided to sever ties with her children and her grandchildren, for reasons that were not explored at the time by Prof. W. D. This physician came anyway to the conclusion that the woman was suffering from a serious personality disorder, associated with a chronic mood disorder, and that she no longer believed in her functional recovery and in the success of any pharmacological option. He therefore agreed to become her attending physician in the path aimed at euthanasia, instructing her to consult a second psychiatrist (Dr. V.), as required by Belgian law.

The meeting between the woman and Dr. V. took place on 17 December 2011: on that occasion, the specialist confirmed the chronic depressive picture from which the patient was suffering, albeit with “ups and downs”, concluding that the request for euthanasia was premature, suggesting that she go to another psychiatrist to reset the drug treatment plan.

On December 23, 2011, Prof. W. D. met again the woman who expressed her deep concern of being abandoned and seeing not accepted her request to die with euthanasia while admitting that she was ready to see another psychiatrist (Dr. V. D.), as requested by Dr. V. On that occasion, Mrs. de Troyer spoke about the reasons that had motivated her to break off relations with her two children, in particular with her eldest son, described by the woman as a person she was afraid of due to his aggressiveness. In a subsequent meeting, which took place on January 12, 2012, Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer told Prof. W. D. she was feeling deeply exhausted, confirming her decision not to see her children anymore, specifying that she had yet to be visited by Dr. V. D. because not reachable. Prof. W. D. thus advised her to consult another psychiatrist, Dr. T.

The meeting with the latter took place on January 17, 2012, and during the meeting the woman specified that her daughter, with whom all contact had been interrupted for two years, knew of her request to die by euthanasia specifying that she no longer had anyone in her life, that she was alone, that she felt incurably ill, that she no longer had the stamina to do anything and that she wanted to die as soon as possible. Although she was never hospitalized in a psychiatric environment (this opportunity was never raised by any doctor), Mrs. de Troyer added that she had no faith in psychiatric science. On 20 January 2012, there was a new consultation with Prof. W. D., who agreed to accompany her personally to Dr. V. D. This psychiatrist suggested her to inform the children of her decision to die, so that they could accompany her and be present during the euthanasia procedure. Thus, on 31 January 2012, the woman sent an email to her two children to inform them of her decision, the endless severity of her suffering and her desire to die

with dignity. The son did not reply to her letter, while the daughter replied: although very saddened by the decision, she respected her mother’s will.

On February 7, 2012, Prof. W. D. contacted another psychiatrist, Dr. B., who stated that the woman’s health problem was chronic and no longer treatable on a therapeutic level. The same Dr. B., on the following 10 February, sent a letter to Dr. T. informing her that he had previously met the woman (in 1996) due to a very serious psychopathology probably related to a childhood traumatic experience, highlighting that the prognosis was extremely uncertain and obscure.

On February 14, the patient formalized her euthanasia request in writing, indicating in Prof. W. D. her attending physician. On the same day, Dr. T. signed a report acknowledging that the patient had consulted her several times to inform her of her decision to die in order to put an end to her unbearable and hopeless suffering. In that report, the woman was described as lucid and reasonable even after she had been provided with information on possible therapeutic options, and then concluded that the conditions established by the Belgian law permitted to help her die. The same conclusion was reached on the following February 17 by Dr. V. D., who confirmed the serious social isolation of the woman and her refusal to undergo any further drug therapy.

On February 27, 2012, the patient signed a handwritten declaration acknowledging her intention to donate her body to science; two days later, on February 29, 2012, she made a donation of 2,500 euros to Leif (Levensende Informathieforum), a non-profit association led by Prof. W. D., which also had among its members Drs. T. and V. D.

On 8 and 12 March 2012, Prof. W. D. spoke again with the woman concluding that there were no more prospects for continuing her life.

On March 20, 2012, Mrs. de Troyer met P. D., a person she trusted, confiding to her that she intended to write a farewell letter to her children.

On April 13, 2012, Prof. W. D. and P. D. met again Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer who accepted the idea of writing a letter addressed to her children with the assistance of P. D. At the end of the conversation, Prof. W. D. came to the conclusion that the only reasonable option was euthanasia and set the date for April 19, 2012.

On April 10, 2012, two telephone consultations took place between the woman and the same Prof. W. D. who reassured her regarding her will: the euthanasia act was practiced on the following April 19 by the same Prof. W. D. in the UZ Brussels University Hospital, in the presence of Mr. Samuel Vinck (an attorney) and some friends of the woman.

Information of her death was given to her children on the following 20 April, before the opinion expressed by the federal control commission provided for by Belgian law, co-chaired by the same Prof. W. D., who ascertained the regularity of the euthanasia procedure and the observance of all the criteria established by Belgian law verified by “deux médecins indépendants, qui confirmaient la capacité de la patiente, l’incurabilité de sa pathologie et

l'existence d'une souffrance psychique extrême, insupportable et unapaisable”.

The subsequent complaints expressed to the Judicial Authority by the patient's son T. M., a university professor, accusing of non-compliance with Belgian law and of not having been informed of what had been authorized by the two Belgian doctors, were not followed up; in May 2017 he was informed of the filing of his criminal complaint due to insufficient evidence. Hence, his decision to appeal to the European Court of Justice for the violation of articles 2 and 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR).

Going into the merits of the matter, the Strasbourg judges, without declaring the existence of a conflict between art. 2 of the ECHR and the Belgian law (which, under certain conditions, decriminalized euthanasia), recognized that the strictness of the procedure envisaged by Belgian internal legislation had not been respected because the same Prof. W. D., having personally supervised the euthanasia procedure from the initial request of the woman, could not have expressed any judgment on the merits of his work, and would therefore have had to abstain for reasons of independence and competence.

Thus sanctioning Belgium, but without however addressing the compliance of Belgian law with art. 2 of the ECHR (Bucalo, 2023) and without discussing the robustness of the woman's decision as had been done, however, by the same judges in the Haas sentence against Switzerland (Butturini, 2011) whose protagonist had been a patient suffering from bipolar disorder who had resorted to the Court complaining about the inertia of the country to supply a drug lethal for his assisted suicide, which should have put an end to his unbearable suffering.

Results and Discussion

The Choice to Die with the Help or by the Hand of the Doctor (Medically Assisted Death): Limitations and Safety Profiles in Italy

Beyond the complexity of the case, as it has been reconstructed by the Judges of the European Court of Justice, the human story of Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer raises many questions. Two in particular, for what concerns us here, having to ask what it was:

(1) the robustness of her decision to die by euthanasia as scientific evidence demonstrates that cognitive deficits can represent an important component of MDD (Douglas & Porter, 2009) proving capable of compromising memory, attentional functions and learning (Kriesche et al., 2023) with a worsening of the deficits caused by repeated relapses (Semkovska et al., 2019) and aging (Dotson et al., 2020);

(2) the support (medical, psychological, pharmacological and human) that should have been guaranteed to the woman and with what possible precautions (or guarantee rules) could and should have brought to maturity the decision of the same to put an early end to her life.

The general impression that emerges from the analysis of this sad story is that the doctors consulted by Mrs. de Troyer were particularly attentive to the formal aspects required by Belgian law to finalize the euthanasia request

(existence of a serious pathology and incurable, producing constant and unbearable suffering) but little or nothing was done to offer her that support which could control or contain her suffering. In addition, it seems that her daughter's affection could probably be recovered, and that there was a network of friends and trust on which the woman could still count.

Without questioning the seriousness of the suffering caused by the psycho-pathological condition from which Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer was affected, her protracted state of suffering (albeit between the ups and downs that are normally recorded in these clinical situations), the incomplete control of the depressive symptomatology despite the prolonged pharmacological and psycho-behavioral therapies, the distrust gained towards psychiatric treatments, her social isolation and loss of hope, what appears indisputable is that the robustness of her decision was not subjected to any particular verification and that some of the doctors she interviewed politely declined the invitation or temporarily suspended it, believing that the decision to die at the hands of a doctor required a more complete maturation.

Trying to give a practical answer to these questions, we hypothesized to transfer the human story of Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer to the Italian context (where euthanasia is forbidden) asking ourselves what could have happened if she had asked Italian doctors to help her to die with assisted suicide, a practice permitted within limits and the guarantees provided by the Constitutional Judge in sentence no. 242/2019; sentence with which the art. 580 of the penal code (“Instigating and assisting in suicide”) makes the actor no longer punishable in the hypothesis in which the execution of the intention of suicide, autonomously and freely formed, of the adult person has been facilitated provided that the person is affected by an irreversible pathology, kept in life from life-sustaining treatments, the condition is a source of physical or psychological suffering that the person considers as intolerable, while remaining fully capable of making free and informed decisions.

These conditions and the methods of execution of assisted suicide must then be verified by a public structure of the national health service, subject to the opinion of the territorially competent ethics committee, thus identifying a whole series of constraints – not only procedural but above all substantial – which have set, and they continue to pose, problematic questions, not yet fully resolved.

For example, it is much debated which Ethics Committee is properly required to express its opinion in these cases. In response to the specific question posed by the Minister of Health, on 24 February 2023 the National Bioethics Committee considered that the responsibility should be attributed to the CETs (Territorial Ethics Committees), referred to in the Decree of 26 January 2023 (“Identification of forty territorial ethics committees”), uniformly present in the country.

Another important topic of debate concerns life support, on which there are frankly antithetical ideas, there being those who indicate it in those measures that require the use of artificial means and the support given by machines

and those who, on the contrary, extend it to the entire therapeutic weaponry available to doctors.

Different positions also exist on the validity of the treatment decision, there being those who subordinate it to the person's ability to understand and want, and those who, on the contrary, value the cognitive, affective and emotional aspects of decision making, believing that mental disability can never be neither a valid nor a reasonable reason to discriminate against people (Grahek et al., 2018), with all that it entails on a practical level for the rupture of the presumed ability/incapacity dichotomy, and of that still dominant paradigm which sees legal incapacity as the instrument to give support to those people.

The controversy that exists on the capacity, which is a broad and complex philosophical-political construct, whose polysemy – already verifiable in ordinary language – becomes even more evident in the juridical vocabulary due to the plurality and heterogeneity of the contexts, makes impossible to relate to each other by finding a common cross matrix.

Legal capacity (UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, art. 12), ability to act (law n. 219/2017, art. 1, paragraph 5), ability to understand and want (law n. 219/2017, art. 1, paragraph 1 and art. 5, paragraph 1), inability to look after one's own interests (art. 404 of the civil code), ability to make a will (art. 591 of the civil code), ability to consciously participate in the process (art. 70 criminal procedure code), procedural capacity (art. 75 civil procedure code) and ability to make a free and informed decision (Constitutional Court, ordinance n. 207/2018 and sentence n. 242/2019) are, thus, the so many known and formalized faces of the capacity present in the places of law that confirm its eclectic polysemy, probably exacerbated by the vague links and the overlapping of meanings that infer from the different expressions.

In this way, capacity has become a juridical abstraction that is not easy to classify, also due to the extraordinary resistance that it shows every time one tries to give it a unitary classification, fading – depending on the place – in juridical capacity, in imputability, in ability to act, in that of standing in court, in the ability to make a will and in the ability to understand and want, to quote some of its explanations of dubious significance.

However, it is on the ability to understand and want that refers the law n. 219 of 2017 (Cappelli, 2021). "Regulations on informed consent and advance treatment provisions", whilst the Constitutional Court, in more appropriate terms, has repeatedly referred to the person's ability to make a free and informed decision, without however entering into the merits of how this should be explored.

This is an area on which discussion continues, as there are doubts as to whether the rationality of the scientific model is capable of exploring the quality, authenticity and robustness of decision making, with the rigor envisaged by the method of experimental science, as a reproducible and unquestionable final judgment because it is formulated on the basis of the criteria established by a universal scientific law.

Depressive Disorder, Authenticity and Robustness of End-of-Life Choices

Nonetheless, the Italian legislator, precisely regarding the end of life (law n. 219/2017), has subordinated the legitimacy of the choice of treatment to the integrity of the person's ability to understand and want without hint at what his judgment parameters are in order to reduce the evaluative suggestions often present, even among experts, in the courtrooms (Foucault, 2020).

The question is particularly complex, and some very useful indications have been proposed at an international level in this regard (American Psychiatric Association, 2012; Appelbaum, 2007) to correct trivializing professional styles without generalizing the complexity of situations.

In Italy, the Italian Psychogeriatric Association, AIP (Cembrani et al., 2019), and the Istituto Superiore di Sanità, ISS, did so in relatively recent times which, in an extensive document approved by the Conference of Regions and Autonomous Provinces (Istituto Superiore di Sanità, 2020), gave a definition of the decision-making capacity specifying that its evaluation falls within the sphere of responsibility entrusted to clinicians. These are required to fulfill it with the traditional tools of neuropsychological investigation combined with a careful functional evaluation of what the person can do in real life situations. The evaluation is therefore multidimensional: after the clinical-anamnestic interview, it focuses on the neurological/geriatric dimensions completed by the neuropsychological evaluation and by the diagnostic-instrumental tests aimed at excluding treatable secondary pathological forms.

The assessment involves the use of some international scales, which would allow for the selection of two cohorts of patients:

- a) those with scores on the Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) between 20 and 30 (Clinical Dementia Rating – CDR 0.5-1.5) who would have very mild to mild cognitive limitations;
- b) those with MMSE scores below 20 (CDR equal to or greater than 2.0, i.e. moderate to severe cognitive impairments) who would not be able to give valid consent and who could be further evaluated by the administration of other neurocognitive tests, such as the Mac Arthur Competence Assessment Tool-Treatment (MacCAT-7), a 21-item scale (which takes 15-20 minutes to administer) or with simpler analytical methods such as the University of California San Diego Brief Assessment of Capacity to Consent (UBACC) (Jeste et al., 2007).

Naturally, one wonders, as AIP did, whether these tests are really able of selecting people capable of giving their consent from those unable to do so, who therefore should be initiated towards their legal incapacity, as recommended by the ISS. It should be considered that the MMSE is not a diagnostic tool created for this specific purpose and that the more sophisticated evaluation scales, such as the MacCAT-7, while exploring the domains of reasoning, planning, choice and control (complex cognitive processes), elude other important aspects (e.g., the social, relational, affective and

emotional ones) which certainly affect every choice of life.

In fact, rationality is an extraordinarily complex process, often fallible because it can be influenced by many choice alternatives, which are in turn influenced by not only cognitive but also emotional, social and environmental processes.

At this point, we should ask ourselves if the selection of those who are able to make a treatment decision from those who are not can be operated with these diagnostic tools and if the traditional scientific model, with its logical spectrum with a hypothetical-deductive matrix, is a tool suitable for achieving this specific purpose and whether or not it complies with the provisions of art. 12 of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) (Cembrani et al., 2022) and the need not to discriminate against people in the exercise of their freedom rights.

However, the question remains open, even if what is beyond dispute is that the decision to die of Madame de Troyer was not targeted by any particular verification, whose robustness was taken for granted by the two doctors who finalized her euthanasia, without considering that major depressive disorder is capable of:

- interfering with the generative process of emotional responses (Joorman & Stanton, 2016) due to a frequent distortion of information caused by cognitive biases in interpretation and memory processes;

- to compromise – more or less severely – the domains of memory, attention and executive functions (Marazziti et al., 2010) with overall cognitive dysfunction emerging in demanding rather than automatic processes (Hartlage et al., 2018).

The result is impaired executive functions and a dysregulation of emotion control (Vazquez & Hernangómez, 2009).

The result is also a reduced cognitive control over the cognitive biases that make depressive symptoms chronic and dysregulation in the control of negative emotions (Grahek et al., 2018) the neurobiological cause of which could be identified in the reduced functioning of the anterior cingulate cortex, of the ventral prefrontal cortex (Beavers, 2005) and the dorsolateral one (Li et al., 2010). What really were the cognitive impairments of Mrs. Godelieva de Troyer is evident from the reconstruction of the facts carried out by the Judges of the European Court of Justice: the robustness of her decision-making capacity has been only partially investigated.

Only by Dr. T. the woman was described as lucid and reasonable, even if it is not known whether these general notes have been confirmed by a more in-depth test evaluation so as to investigate those cognitive and emotional domains (and, with them, suggestibility) that may be negatively affected by major depressive disorder. *On the Need to Also Give Depressed People the Necessary Support for the Maturation of Life Choices*

In addition to evaluating the robustness of Mrs. de Troyer's decision-making capacity, we still have to ask ourselves in what concrete ways her taking charge could and should have been strengthened with the aim of

coping with her loneliness, loss of hope and unbearable suffering.

Her contacts with the Belgian doctors, as confirmed by the procedural reconstruction of the affair, were repeated – this cannot be denied – but what seems to emerge is their ritual formality with the apparent renunciation of making any useful attempt to give the woman the support and comfort she needed.

This could have been achieved not only by setting up a new therapeutic plan which, probably, would not have had the desired effect (due to the patient's weak compliance, also testified by her most complete distrust in psychiatric care), but above all by providing her with the psychological support that the Italian law of 2017 confirmed to be indispensable in all cases of therapeutic refusal.

Support that could have strengthened relationships with friends and recovered the family affections that Mrs. de Troyer had interrupted for little-investigated reasons, even admitting that her inner feeling could be influenced by the aggressive behavior of her son, who later became the true and only protagonist of the judicial dispute initiated for the alleged violation of Belgian law, which was then examined by the Supreme Court of Justice.

Moreover, her relationship with her daughter was not completely severed by the latter, given her reply to her mother's email in which she declared that she accepted her decision to die, albeit with great pain. This confirms that an attempt should have been made in re-establishing family relations, if only for a better accompaniment of the woman in her last life project.

However, friends (who therefore existed) took part in it. Mr. P. D., met on 20 March 2012, and described as a trusted person, was the one the woman confided the inner need to write a farewell letter addressed to her children.

Conclusions

Formulating definitive conclusions from cases that have reached trial in the courtrooms is almost always a gamble, not only because the procedural reconstruction of events usually shows profiles of incompleteness but above all because the decision taken in sentence by the Judges is a confounding factor that may influence the final comment.

Nonetheless, news stories are an extraordinary training ground that motivates and trains reflection.

In the story here described, we wanted to try our hand without the ambition of arriving at an absolute truth.

The case of Mrs. de Troyer raises many questions concerning the robustness of the decision-making capacity of people suffering from major depressive disorder, which – in our opinion – must always be careful and in-depth, considering that their management cannot be limited to the pharmacological approach alone.

This assumes particular importance when the legal asset put at risk is the defence of life.

To all effects – even in the Italian legislation – this is the cornerstone of democratic life, which opens up to all the other rights and freedoms inscribed in the human person.

Ethical Approval

The case involved is a public case (European Court of Human Rights Judgment n. 78017 of 4 October 2022, Mortier vs. Belgique).

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